

SATISFACTORY

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The SatisFactory project consortium is composed of:		
CERTH¹	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
SIGMA	Sigma Orionis SA	France
FRAUNHOFER	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V	Germany
COMAU	Comau SPA	Italy
EPFL	Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
ISMB	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella sulle tecnologie dell'informazione e delle telecomunicazioni	Italy
ABE	Atlantis Engineering AE	Greece
REGOLA	Regola srl	Italy
SUNLIGHT	Systems Sunlight Industrial & Commercial Company of Defensive, Energy, Electronic and Telecommunication Systems S.A.	Greece
GlassUP	GlassUp srl	Italy

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¹ Project Coordinator

AUTHORS LIST

Leading Author (Editor)				
Surname		First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
Cultrona		Pietro Alberto	COMAU	Pietro.cultrona@comau.com
Co-authors (in alphabetic order)				
#	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Brizzi	Paolo	ISMB	brizzi@ismb.it
2	Elmasllari	Erion	Fraunhofer FIT	erion.elmasllari@fit.fraunhofer.de
3	Ippolito	Massimo	COMAU	MASSIMO.IPPOLITO@comau.com
4	Jentsch	Marc	Fraunhofer FIT	marc.jentsch@fit.fraunhofer.de
5	Kakabegas	Akis	CERTH	akakabek@cperi.certh.gr
6	Matiouk	Svetlana	Fraunhofer FIT	svetlana.matiouk@fit.fraunhofer.de
7	Mautino	Sara	GlassUP	sara@glassup.net
8	Elsianli	Katerina	ABE	elsianli@abe.gr
9	Parcharidis	Symeon	SUNLIGHT	s.parcharidis@sunlight.gr
10	Rusinà	Fulvio	COMAU	Fulvio.rusina@comau.com
11	Turinetto	Maurizio	Regola	m.turinetto@regola.it
12	Voutetakis	Spyros	CERTH	paris@cperi.certh.gr
13	Ziougou	Chrysovalantou	CERTH	ziougou@cperi.certh.gr

REVIEWERS LIST

List of Reviewers (in alphabetic order)				
#	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Dos Santos	Stephanie	SIGMA	stephanie.dos-santos@sigma-orionis.com
2	Ioannidis	Dimos	CERTH	djoannid@iti.gr
3	Metaxa	Ifigeneia	ABE	metaxa@abe.gr

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
APAC	Asia-Pacific
AR	Augmented Reality
BW	Body Welding
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
EC	European Commission
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EU	European Union
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
ICT	Information & Communications Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MLD	Multi-Layered Description
OPC	OLE (Object Linking and Embedding) for Process Control
OP-MLD	Operating Procedures Multi-Layered Description
PC	Personal Computer
R&D	Research & Development
RFID	Radio-frequency identification
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
SMLC	Smart Manufacturing Leadership Coalition
SOTA	State-Of-The-Art
UWB	Ultra Wideband Technology
WCM	World Class Manufacturing

WP	Workpackage
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020), reporting the results of the activities carried out by WP1.

SatisFactory aims to contribute to the transformation of traditional industrial environments using cutting-edge technologies in ways that are both productive and appealing to youth.

For this aim, WP1 will manage and undertake the work in carrying out the iterative engineering of requirements, which special focuses on the engineering process of initial requirements and reengineering after the end of each iteration cycle.

The purpose of this Workpackage is thus to maintain a continuous discovery and analysis of user centric requirements, needs and prospects, to be used in the design, development, implementation and validation of the SatisFactory platform and services.

The main objective of this deliverable is to describe the requirements of the prototype applications for the three end-users test-beds: discrete manufacturing in automotive, discrete manufacturing for batteries and continuous process in chemical applications. Specifically, the goal of this document is to define the a list of initial requirements exploiting the "Volere" approach, that will be continuously updated and refined through an iterative process that will lead to the production of a total of three releases of this document, respectively in Project Months M4, M14 and M26.

In particular, it is worth to highlight that the collection of requirements, performed through more than forty (40) face-to-face interviews of end-user employees, followed by brainstorming sessions among technology partners, provided more than eighty-three (83) initial requirements. Following key requirement areas are provided:

- Manufacturing process monitoring & verification
- Production & maintenance documents access and guidelines
- Workload planning
- Training procedures
- Safety, ergonomics & privacy
- Communication, IoT and smart sensing
- Gestures recognition and vocal interaction
- Middleware & platform

These topics will be the main areas of improvement that the SatisFactory project will consider during the future development phases performed in the technical Workpackages and validated through an iterative process.

This deliverable, after the introductory chapter, presents in Chapter 2 the requirements engineering approach and the Volere methodology adopted, giving details on the web-portal used to maintain the requirements database.

The following, Chapter 3, depicts the production processes, as well as the actors and stakeholders considered in the SatisFactory project. The first section gives the main definitions, while the second one introduces details of the considered manufacturing processes with the associated workers involved for each domain.

In Chapter 4, the process adopted to collect the user requirements and the main results of the interviews performed are presented. This activity was conducted through face-to-face interviews in the premises of the three considered industrial sectors.

Finally, the key messages extracted from each end-user, including their transposition in the Volere Requirements template, are described Chapter 5.

1. INTRODUCTION

SatisFactory aims to contribute to the transformation of traditional industrial environments using cutting-edge technologies in ways that are both productive and appealing to youth.

The fundamental component of the proposed system will be the assessment and storage of the explicit and tacit knowledge created on the shop floor by aggregating a set of heterogeneous smart devices and sensors and extracting context-aware information based on their measurements. The distribution of this knowledge will be based on 3 important system tools: a training platform to allow the fast and intuitive education of employees; a collaboration platform, to stimulate and promote team interactions; ubiquitous user interfaces to support all employees seamlessly in real time and on the move.

SatisFactory will also utilize the aggregated knowledge in order to leverage the control and re-adaptation of facilities and streamline the workload. In order to enhance working experience and thus increase the workplace attractiveness, augmented reality and gamification approaches will be utilized. Additionally modern wearable devices will allow the interaction of workers with the system without disrupting their workflow. Validation will assess the impact and reveal the capabilities of SatisFactory towards the promotion of novel and viable business models for increased innovation potential, flexibility and productivity, while enhancing workplace attractiveness.

1.1 *PURPOSE, CONTEXT AND SCOPE OF THIS DELIVERABLE*

The purpose of this deliverable is to give a systematic formalization of an initial set of relevant specifications, necessary to the development of the prototype application. This document describes the method to support user requirements analysis adapting it to the different environments involved in the SatisFactory project and providing a full overview about the requirements.

These requirements will guide the development phases within the technical work packages, and therefore, this deliverable will be the first common source of user requirements for the SatisFactory consortium. The list of requirements in this document reflects the work performed in Tasks T1.1 – “End-user and shop floor, system requirements and specifications”, T1.3 – “Use Cases and Scenarios” and T1.5 – “Guidelines for Deployment”, and emerged from the interview process conducted with representatives from the three application domains of the SatisFactory project: discrete manufacturing in automotive, discrete manufacturing for batteries and continuous process in chemical applications.

Specifically, the goal of the deliverable is to define a list of initial requirements exploiting the “Volere” approach, that will be continuously updated and refined through an iterative process that will lead to the production of a total of three releases of this document, respectively in Project Months M4, M14 and M26.

The development of this deliverable was coordinated by Comau with contribution of CERTH, SUNLIGHT, ABE-ATLANTIS, FRAUNHOFER FIT, ISMB, REGOLA and GLASSUP.

1.2 BACKGROUND

This deliverable belongs to WP₁ - Domain Analysis and Requirements Engineering, which is dedicated to the definition of the requirements for a safer and more attractive shop-floor environment and the guidelines and recommendations for design and deployment of SatisFactory applications in end-users test-beds. Within the Work Package, more specifically, tasks T1.1 and T1.3 are focused on development of user and system requirements according to the use case and scenarios analysed in the project, while task t1.5 intends to study the needs and requirements that should be fulfilled to guarantee successful deployment of the technologies developed in the SatisFactory project.

Manufacturing is a key enabler for European societal challenges, to this aim, the EFFRA association (European Factories of the Future Research Association), developed a multi-annual roadmap (EFFRA 2013), to guide the manufacturing research programs that will lead to more innovative manufacturing approaches.

Europe is heavily investing in maintaining its manufacturing excellence nowadays, facing the high level of competitiveness of APAC countries from one side and the recent revamping of the US manufacturing from the other.

The Horizon 2020 program strategy emphasises the need for organising and designing manufacturing in a way which ensures that manufacturing enterprises will remain socially sustainable while still achieving global competitiveness. To resolve these issues, interdisciplinary research and innovation is needed to provide the basis for the design of adequate manufacturing environments and workplaces. As a result, human capability and machine intelligence will be integrated within production systems that can achieve maximum efficiency as well as worker satisfaction. Research efforts should tackle social sustainability challenges at all levels of manufacturing industries. This effort will be economically very successful, while still improving corporate social responsibility, inclusive workplace design, and efficient use of ICT to leverage the competence of the European workforce.

Increasing complexity of manufacturing systems and processes creates the need for knowledge-workers to be supported by appropriate tools providing them with assistance for operations along the entire production chain in factories and further development of their competences. There is a clear need to contextualise from complex documentation. Appropriate interfaces (e.g. visual, audio, etc.) and assistance tools for knowledge communication will assist workers while performing manufacturing operations, including assembly, operation of machines, maintenance activities, ramp-up procedures, troubleshooting and remote guidance. Advanced human-machine interfaces for workers are required, considering:

- 1 usability and the related learning process;
- 2 physical, sensorial and cognitive interaction; and
- 3 fulfilment of safety and health conditions during human-machine interaction.

The expected, extensive collaboration between future knowledge-workers and robots (as well as other advanced automation equipment) will be crucial for successful human-centred design.

ICT can play a pivotal role in making manufacturing more attractive through the development of tools and methodologies, such as serious games, demonstrators and social networks that engage the potential workforce from an early stage. Procedures to identify and reinforce the capacity of workers to remain motivated during their working day need also to be investigated. Furthermore, ICT could give more engagement opportunities such as product design and app development to the

younger generation who are already technology savvy and adept at problem solving through programming in the mobile environment. Future ICT research should develop metrics and feedback mechanisms to understand the impact on younger generations.

After EFFRA, also other associations have focused the industry innovation, in particular the German industry has developed a reference framework named Industrie 4.0 (hightech-strategie.de) with the main goal of preparing the German industry for the next industrial revolution. Priorities of this program are the Horizontal and vertical system integration, Normalisation and standardization, Logistics and finally Labour and organisation. This last point includes aspects such as workers safety and satisfaction, as well as innovative workplace design, "since good jobs are an important basis for creative ideas and economic innovation"

In parallel to EFFRA and Industrie 4.0 activities, in USA the SMLC Smart Manufacturing Leadership Coalition, is targeting the innovation activities in US manufacturing. Main priorities of this industry coalition are Additive manufacturing, Lightweight and modern metals, Next generation power electronics as well as Digital manufacturing & design, with the main scope of promoting 'American-made' and retaining jobs.

2. APPROACH & METHODOLOGY

2.1 HUMAN-CENTERED DESIGN PROCESS

In order for Satisfactory to fulfil its goals, it needs to closely communicate, be guided from, and be led from the people on the factory floor. They are the target of our project, and at the same time the key to understanding how their work life can be improved and how others can be inspired to work in factories. In this environment, the best approach is User Centered Design. Its characteristics are:

- the design is based upon an explicit understanding of users, tasks and environments
- users are involved throughout design and development
- the design is driven and refined by user evaluations
- the process is iterative
- the design addresses the whole user experience
- the design team includes multidisciplinary skills and perspectives

The approach is rooted on domain analysis and interaction with the workers and other stakeholders. Design and development follows from the insights acquired during domain analysis, in an iterative manner. They grow from simple, paper-based sketches, to prototypes, and to final products. As a crucial step in every iteration, prototypes and concepts are evaluated by users to check that they progress in the right course towards fulfilling the users' needs and the project's aims.

2.1.1 General ISO 9241-210 process model

In the words of the ISO 9241-210 Standard:

Using a human-centred approach to design and development has substantial economic and social benefits for users, employers and suppliers. Highly usable systems and products tend to be more successful both technically and commercially.

The process model introduced by ISO 9241-210 for Human Centered Design is depicted in Figure 1:

Figure 1 ISO9241-210 Process Model

In this process model, work starts with understanding the context of use, i.e. the users, tools, tasks, social and physical environments where the developed system will be used and whose needs it will fulfil. (See also Section 2.2.1).

Once some (partial) understanding of the context has been reached, requirements are derived from it. These, especially in the beginning, take the form of user requirements, i.e. what the user needs from the system. Only in a later iteration, when the system starts to take a concrete shape, are these requirements transformed into system requirements, i.e. what the system must offer or how the architecture should look like.

Based on requirements, a prototype of the system is created in the third step. This can be as simple as a paper prototype or scenario for the first iterations, or as complex as a beta-version of the software in the later iterations. The prototype is, however, not a goal in itself, but only a tool that allows us to verify -- evaluate -- with the users, whether we have understood correctly what they need. The prototype is, in a sense, an embodiment of our understanding of the context. The evaluation usually yields new knowledge about the context, points out things that were forgotten or underestimated, as well as approaches that seem to work. Based on this, the picture of the context is corrected, widened, or better defined, and the cycle starts anew.

2.2 METHODS FOR CONTEXT OF USE RESEARCH

2.2.1 Context of use definition

The data describing the Context of Use can be organised according to the four major categories: i) Users, ii) their tasks and goals, iii) tools and environment, iv) workflows as well as organisational and social surroundings.

Insights on factors influencing work satisfaction of the shop-floor workers could be related to any of these categories, since the entire context of use (or in the case of SatisFactory we could say "context of work") is important for a pleasant working experience. Thus, it is suggested to highlight the key factors that – based on the ethnographic data gathered during the user research, e.g. interviews and observations – are especially contributing to satisfaction of the workers.

In the following some examples for the types of data for each category are given.

2.2.1.1 ***Users***

- Skills, expertise, competence
- Pre-knowledge and –experience
- Roles and Education
- Motoric and sensory abilities
- Expectations of the technology: Content, functionality, design

2.2.1.2 ***Tasks and goals***

- Activities targeted at the achievement of a goal
- Considering frequency and duration
- Goals and motivation of the user, provider, supplier, vendor
- Business and marketing goals

2.2.1.3 ***Tools and environment***

- Surrounding conditions (hardware, software, equipment,...)
- Environment of use (office, home, mobile, ...)
- Competitors

2.2.1.4 ***Workflows, Organizational and social surrounding***

- Work processes
- Current legislation
- Law of nature
- Instructions / Regulations / Standards / Best Practices
- Corporate culture

Figure 2: Overview of the Context of Use

2.2.2 Analytic methods

2.2.2.1 Literature research

The central question of Satisfactory is, in essence, the same question that Human Resources Management Science has been asking itself for many years: How to motivate people and improve their satisfaction? The Satisfactory approach, however, looks at this question from the technological support point of view. It is very useful to look at other approaches, both technological and otherwise, in order to learn from them. Literature research is the best method to achieve this goal and will provide us with a frame within which the Satisfactory tools and systems have to exist.

2.2.2.2 Document analysis

Work processes, environments, and rules are described and regulated in highly detailed ways. Some of this is defined by legal frameworks, other parts by company-internal regulations. There is, in essence, a very rigid frame within which Satisfactory artefacts and solutions have to work. For that very reason, document analysis -- regulations, rules, job descriptions, HR reports, and any other relevant data must be studied and used to understand the frame as well as to find out what opportunities and support it can also offer to the project. Document analysis should be used only in conjunction with ethnographic methods (Section 2.2.3), because they typically present a wished-for state, but not the way work is done in the real world.

2.2.3 Ethnographic methods

By examining how people actually communicate and work together, the ethnographic approach enables us to understand how people face the daily challenges at work, what they consider as normal, what they see as positive, and what is tiring and problematic and should be changed. The aim is to reveal ways in which collaboration is done practically, as well as "holes" and socio-physical structures which a technology approach can fill and support accordingly.

2.2.3.1 *Interviews*

'Insider accounts' from people who work in factories can provide critical insight into what makes them work at a factory, what motivates them, and what needs to be improved. A range of interviewing techniques will be used:

Semi-structured interviews utilise a prepared list of questions, based on literature review, existing domain and problem knowledge, etc. However, it is allowed to stray from the plan if the conversation leads into interesting areas that were not anticipated in the list. The main point is to watch out for interesting remarks and follow up with new, on-the-spot questions to probe deeper.

Ethnographic interviews combine observation and questions, to gain insight into environmental contexts, communication and practice of the job. The idea is to interview users in their settings, possibly while they are performing tasks, asking questions about what they are doing, how they do things and why along the way, or asking them to think out loud and perform walk-throughs of their job with the researchers.

2.2.3.2 *Observations*

It is easy to read how work should be done by the book. However, to really understand how it is done in practice, observation is crucial. People often stray from the rules of the book; it is said that the most effective way to strike is to do everything by the book: Work will simply stop because the rules don't foresee every possible situation.

Ethnographic studies of work practices have been used very effectively to inform IT systems design (e.g. Button 2000; Heath et al. 2010; Suchman 1997). Such studies do not simply generate requirements, but rather represent an enquiry which supports further design and discussions with stakeholders.

2.2.3.3 *Participant observation*

Participant observation consists of following and observing workers' activities attentively, with a focus on how they interact with the social and material worlds around them, with environments, technologies, artefacts and materials. Researchers should simply follow activities as they happen.

2.2.4 *Research through design*

2.2.4.1 *Scenarios*

Scenarios are a free form narrative that tells the existing practices as well as future visions of a product or system being developed. Scenarios normally do not explain the details of the interaction or the system; they are purposefully left rough and vague in order to avoid users hanging onto details and overlooking the general issue of whether the vision expressed by the scenario fits in their world and fulfils their needs.

2.2.4.2 *Co-Design*

User-centered design puts the user in focus, but allows design to happen in a lab, far from the place of use. While easier to carry out, design in a lab has been shown to be problematic, because the rest

of the context cannot be completely transplanted into the lab environment. The ways in which people appropriate and use technologies are highly dependant on what's available in their environment. In co-design, the distinction between users, designers, and researchers blurs, and they all work together, in place, to design a working solution that fits the context of use and the needs of the users.

2.2.4.3 *Prototyping*

Prototypes put something concrete in front of the stakeholders, so that all discussion can be done at the same level and towards a concrete, possible implementation of the system. It is important for prototypes to be visibly unfinished, so people don't waste time discussing about unimportant details but rather about the important general concepts.

2.3 SATISFACTORY REQUIREMENTS ENGINEERING APPROACH

SatisFactory is using the Volere Requirements approach described in (Robertson and Robertson 1999; Robertson and Robertson 2004; Robertson and Robertson 2010). Volere is a proven and widely used general-purpose approach to requirements elicitation, including both the process of eliciting requirements as well as the format for representing them. Section 2.3.1 provides an overview of key elements of the Volere approach. In particular, subsection 2.3.1.3 provides descriptions of the content and motivation for the 33 Volere requirement types being used in SatisFactory. These descriptions serve as reference for understanding the SatisFactory requirements given in Chapter 5 - Key topics and Requirements.

To suit the particular needs of an international research project, SatisFactory has integrated adapted elements of the Volere approach into the SatisFactory design approach. Relevant details on this adaptation and integration are described in sections 2.3.2 and 2.3.3.

2.3.1 Volere requirements approach

The Volere requirements approach is described in (Robertson and Robertson 1999; Robertson and Robertson 2004) There is also a web-site dedicated to the Volere approach here:

<http://www.volere.co.uk/>

One of the various resources available on this site is the so-called "Volere Requirements Specification Template" (Robertson and Robertson 2010).

Moreover, there is a very active community around the Volere approach on LinkedIn:

<http://www.linkedin.com/groups/Volere-Requirements-2491512>

This community is highly valuable for obtaining practical guidance for applying the Volere approach and for requirements elicitation in general.

The Volere approach defines 27 sections for the requirements specification, as presented in 2.3.1.3. Each of these sections contains one or more subsection. Altogether Volere defines almost 100 subsections for a complete Volere requirements specification. Out of these, 33 subsections correspond to different types of requirements. The other subsections of the specification correspond to other, auxiliary information, such as use-cases.

The 33 requirement types share the same representation format, which is called the "Requirements Shell". This format is further explained in subsection 2.3.1.1.

The Volere approach also defines a process model for the entire requirements process. This process model is further explained in subsection 2.3.1.2.

2.3.1.1 *Requirements Shell*

Figure 3 reproduces the generic Volere "Requirements Shell" from (Robertson and Robertson 2010). While the "Requirements Shell" mimics an index card, it is meant as the definition of a representational format that should be used with appropriate technical support for authoring requirements.

The specific technical support adopted in SatisFactory is described in subsection 2.3.3. Because of this support and also because of a number of adaptations of Volere for the purposes of the project, the requirement shell actually used in SatisFactory slightly differs from the generic one.

For instance, SatisFactory uses the simpler MoSCoW (Wikipedia 2015) scheme for requirements prioritization instead of the customer satisfaction and dissatisfaction ratings that are often confusing.

Arguably the two most important fields of the Requirements Shell are "Rationale" and "Fit Criterion". In conjunction with the short "Description" field, they support requirements authors in separating different concerns.

The "Description" is reserved for stating the requirement as factually and concisely as possible. The "Rationale" requires the author to provide an argument for the requirement which may then be contested in the requirements process. The "Fit Criterion" finally requires the author to provide a test for deciding whether a given design actually meets the present requirement. The test needs to be specified in such a way that it is clear how the test can be carried out.

Figure 3: The Volere "Requirements Shell" for representing so-called atomic requirements.

2.3.1.2 *Volere Process Model*

The Volere process model comprehensively describes the various stages, actors and artefacts that comprise the dynamic execution of the Volere approach. The overview of this process model is shown in "2.3.1.2 - *Volere Process Model*".

Each of the numbered process steps can be expanded further, illustrating that the overall Volere process model is rather comprehensive and can become relatively complex to carry out.

Depending on the size of the project, the different steps can be carried out with greater or smaller detail and number of iterations, allowing the process to be scaled to the respective needs and available resources. Four steps merit further discussion.

First, "Prototype the Requirements" addresses the important aspect that it is often very difficult to define a fixed set of requirements for implementation. Especially for innovative products this is because

- requirements are often difficult to describe precisely
- requirements are often difficult to assess with respect to their relative merit
- requirements that conflict are often difficult to balance

To address these challenges, SatisFactory makes systematic use of the prototyping techniques during the course of the project work. See also (Gomaa and Scott 1981) for the role of prototyping in requirements engineering.

Second, "Taking Stock of the Specification" addresses the equally important aspect that requirements do not exist alone but always have to be understood in the context of the other requirements that have been defined for the given design. That is to say that the requirements process does not end with authoring individual requirements. In fact, in-depth analysis of the growing set of requirements throughout the requirements process and continued refinement of the requirements (Sutcliffe et al 2003) is paramount to achieving a high-quality specification.

Figure 4: Overview of the Volere Process Model

Third, the "Quality Gateway" addresses the likewise important aspect that requirements can have largely varying quality. This includes both the completeness of the requirement shell as described in subsection 2.3.1.1 as well as the quality of each individual field. The Volere approach recommends an explicit "Quality Gateway" that each requirement has to pass before it can become part of the specification.

Moreover, we employ a specific scheme for formulating user needs (as part of "Stakeholder Wants and Needs"). It is presented in Figure 4. Strict following this syntax supports a correct formulation of the user need according to the definition below.

Definition:

User need – A necessary pre-condition allowing to efficiently fulfill the purpose contained in an actual situation of the context of use.

Furthermore, the syntax helps including two important characteristics in the formulation:

- User needs always refer to and justify what happens in the context of use.
- User needs always consist of a pre-condition (state) and a purpose this pre-condition serves.

Another important aspect to bear in mind when formulating user needs is that they intrinsically affiliate with the problem space. Thus, wording that belongs to the solution space or is related to a concrete technology like "system", "document", "pencil", "keyboard", "press button", "editor", "barcode scanner" etc. should be strongly avoided.

Figure 5: Syntax for formulating user needs

2.3.1.3 Reference for Volere Requirement Types

According to the Volere methodology all information that is part of the requirements specification is viewed as belonging to a particular type. This classification should ease the use of the existing requirements and the coordination between the different experts working on the same project. Altogether there are 33 requirement types that are a subset of the close to 100 subsections of the 27 sections of the Volere requirements specification. In the following Volere requirement types are listed and briefly explained.

Overview

Project Drivers

1. The Purpose of the Project
2. The Stakeholders

Project Constraints

3. Mandated Constraints
4. Naming Conventions and Terminology
5. Relevant Facts and Assumptions

Functional Requirements

6. The Scope of the Work

7. Business Data Model & Data Dictionary
8. The Scope of the Product
9. Functional Requirements

Non-functional Requirements

10. Look and Feel Requirements
11. Usability and Humanity Requirements
12. Performance Requirements
13. Operational and Environmental Requirements
14. Maintainability and Support Requirements
15. Security Requirements
16. Cultural and Political Requirements
17. Legal Requirements

Project Issues

18. Open Issues
19. Off-the-Shelf Solutions
20. New Problems
21. Tasks
22. Migration to the New Product
23. Risks
24. Costs
25. User Documentation and Training
26. Waiting Room
27. Ideas for Solutions

Solution Constraints (3a)

Content *This specifies constraints on the way that the problem must be solved. Describe the mandated technology or solution. Include any appropriate version numbers. You should also explain the reason for using the technology.*

Motivation *To identify constraints that guide the final product. Your client, customer, or user may have design preferences, or only certain solutions may be acceptable. If these constraints are not met, your solution is not acceptable.*

Functional Requirements (9a)

Content *This is a specification for each atomic functional requirement. As for all types of atomic requirements (functional, non-functional, constraint), use the requirements shell as a guide for which attributes should be specified. A full explanation of the atomic requirement and its attributes is included in this template's introductory material.*

Motivation *To specify the detailed functional requirements to be carried out by the product.*

Appearance Requirements (10a)

Content *The section contains requirements relating to the spirit of the product. Your client may have made particular demands for the product, such as corporate branding, colours to be used, and so on. This section captures the requirements for the appearance. Do not attempt to design it until the appearance requirements are known.*

Motivation *To ensure that the appearance of the product conforms to the organization's expectations.*

Style Requirements (10b)

Content *Requirements that specify the mood, style, or feeling of the product, which influences the way a potential customer will see the product. Also, the stakeholders' intentions for the amount of interaction the user is to have with the product.*

In this section, you would also describe the appearance of the package if this is to be a manufactured product. The package may have some requirements as to its size, style, and consistency with other packages put out by your organization. Keep in mind the European laws on packaging, which require that the package not be significantly larger than the product it encloses.

The style requirements that you record here will guide the designers to create a product as envisioned by your client.

Motivation *Given the state of today's market and people's expectations, we cannot afford to build products that have the wrong style. Once the functional requirements are satisfied, it is often the appearance and style of products that determine whether they are successful. Your task in this section is to determine precisely how the product shall appear to its intended consumer.*

Ease of Use Requirements (11a)

Content *This section describes your client's aspirations for how easy it is for the intended users of the product to operate it. The product's usability is derived from the abilities of the expected users of the product and the complexity of its functionality.*

The usability requirements should cover properties such as these:

- *Efficiency of use: How quickly or accurately the user can use the product.*
- *Ease of remembering: How much the casual user is expected to remember about using the product.*
- *Error rates: For some products it is crucial that the user commits very few, or no, errors.*
- *Overall satisfaction in using the product: This is especially important for commercial, interactive products that face a lot of competition. Web sites are a good example.*
- *Feedback: How much feedback the user needs to feel confident that the product is actually accurately doing what the user expects. The necessary degree of feedback will be higher for some products (e.g., safety-critical products) than for others.*

Motivation *To guide the product's designers toward building a product that meets the expectations of its eventual users.*

Personalization and Internationalization Requirements (11b)

Content *This section describes the way in which the product can be altered or configured to take into account the user's personal preferences or choice of language.*

The personalization requirements should cover issues such as the following:

- *Languages, spelling preferences, and language idioms*
- *Currencies, including the symbols and decimal conventions*
- *Personal configuration options*

Motivation *To ensure that the product's users do not have to struggle with, or meekly accept, the builder's cultural conventions.*

Learning Requirements (11c)

Content *Requirements specifying how easy it should be to learn to use the product. This learning curve ranges from zero time for products intended for placement in the public domain (e.g., a parking meter or a web site) to a considerable amount of time for complex, highly technical products. (We know of one product where it was necessary for graduate engineers to spend 18 months in a training program before being qualified to use the product.)*

Motivation *To quantify the amount of time that your client feels is allowable before a user can successfully use the product. This requirement guides designers to understand how users will learn the product. For example, designers may build elaborate interactive help facilities into the product, or the product may be packaged with a tutorial. Alternatively, the product may have to be constructed so that all of its functionality is apparent upon first encountering it.*

Understandability and Politeness Requirements (11d)

Content *This specifies the requirement for the product to be understood by its users. While "usability" refers to ease of use, efficiency, and similar characteristics, "understandability" determines whether the users instinctively know what the product will do for them and how it fits into their view of the world. You can think of understandability as the product being polite to its users and not expecting them to know or learn things that have nothing to do with their business problem. Another aspect of politeness is that the product should not expect the user to input any information to which the product already has access.*

Motivation *To avoid forcing users to learn terms and concepts that are part of the product's internal construction and are not relevant to the users' world. To make the product more comprehensible and thus more likely to be adopted by its intended users.*

Accessibility Requirements (11e)

Content *The requirements for how easy it should be for people with common disabilities to access the product. These disabilities might be related to physical disability or visual, hearing, cognitive, or other abilities.*

Motivation *In many countries it is required that some products be made available to people facing certain types of disabilities. In any event, it is self-defeating to exclude this sizable community of potential customers.*

Speed and Latency Requirements (12a)

Content *Specifies the amount of time available to complete specified tasks. These requirements often refer to response times. They can also refer to the product's ability to operate at a speed suitable for the intended environment.*

Motivation *Some products—usually real-time products—must be able to perform some of their functionality within a given time slot. Failure to do so may mean catastrophic failure (e.g., a ground-sensing radar in an airplane fails to detect an upcoming mountain) or the product will not cope with the required volume of use (e.g., an automated ticket-selling machine).*

Safety-Critical Requirements (12b)

Content *Quantification of the perceived risk of damage to people, property, and environment. Different countries have different standards, so the fit criteria must specify precisely which standards the product must meet.*

Motivation *To understand and highlight the damage that could potentially occur when using the product within the expected operational environment.*

Precision or Accuracy Requirements (12c)

Content *Quantification of the desired accuracy of the results produced by the product.*

Motivation *To set the client's and users' expectations for the precision of the product.*

Reliability and Availability Requirements (12d)

Content *This section quantifies the necessary reliability of the product. The reliability is usually expressed as the allowable time between failures, or the total allowable failure rate. This section also quantifies the expected availability of the product.*

Motivation *It is critical for some products not to fail too often. This section allows you to explore the possibility of failure and to specify realistic levels of service. It also gives you the opportunity to set the client's and users' expectations about the amount of time that the product will be available for use.*

Robustness or Fault-Tolerance Requirements (12e)

Content *Robustness specifies the ability of the product to continue to function under abnormal circumstances.*

Motivation *To ensure that the product is able to provide some or all of its services after or during some abnormal happening in its environment.*

Capacity Requirements (12f)

Content *This section specifies the volumes that the product must be able to deal with and the amount of data stored by the product.*

Motivation *To ensure that the product is capable of processing the expected volumes.*

Scalability or Extensibility Requirements (12g)

Content *This specifies the expected increases in size that the product must be able to handle. As a business grows (or is expected to grow), our software products must increase their capacities to cope with the new volumes.*

Motivation *To ensure that the designers allow capacity for future growth.*

Longevity Requirements (12h)

Content *This specifies the expected lifetime of the product.*

Motivation *To ensure that the product is built based on an understanding of expected return on investment.*

Expected Physical Environment (13a)

Content *This section specifies the physical environment in which the product will operate.*

Motivation *To highlight conditions that might need special requirements, preparations, or training. These requirements ensure that the product is fit to be used in its intended environment.*

Requirements for Interfacing with Adjacent Systems (13b)

Content *This section describes the requirements to interface with partner applications and/or devices that the product needs to successfully operate.*

Motivation *Requirements for the interfaces to other applications often remain undiscovered until implementation time. Avoid a high degree of rework by discovering these requirements early.*

Productization Requirements (13c)

Content *Any requirements that are necessary to make the product into a distributable or saleable item. It is also appropriate to describe here the operations needed to install a software product successfully.*

Motivation *To ensure that if work must be done to get the product out the door, then that work becomes part of the requirements. Also, to quantify the client's and users' expectations about the amount of time, money, and resources they will need to allocate to install the product.*

Release Requirements (13d)

Content *Specification of the intended release cycle for the product and the form that the release shall take.*

Motivation *To make everyone aware of how often you intend to produce new releases of the product.*

Maintenance Requirements (14a)

Content *A quantification of the time necessary to make specified changes to the product.*

Motivation *To make everyone aware of the maintenance needs of the product.*

Supportability Requirements (14b)

Content *This specifies the level of support that the product requires. Support is often provided via a help desk. If people will provide support for the product, that service is considered part of the product: Are there any requirements for that support? You might also build support into the product itself, in which case this section is the place to write those requirements.*

Motivation *To ensure that the support aspect of the product is adequately specified.*

Adaptability Requirements (14c)

Content *Description of other platforms or environments to which the product must be ported.*

Motivation *To publicise the client's and users' expectations about the platforms on which the product will be able to run.*

Access Requirements (15a)

Content *Specification of who is authorized to access to the product (both functionality and data), under what circumstances that access is granted, and to which parts of the product access is allowed.*

Motivation *To understand the expectations for confidentiality aspects of the system.*

Integrity Requirements (15b)

Content *Specification of the required integrity of databases and other files, and of the product itself.*

Motivation *To understand the expectations for the integrity of the product's data. To specify what the product will do to ensure its integrity in the case of an unwanted happening such as attack from the outside or unintentional misuse by an authorized user.*

Privacy Requirements (15c)

Content *Specification of what the product has to do to ensure the privacy of individuals about whom it stores information. The product must also ensure that all laws related to privacy of an individual's data are observed.*

Motivation *To ensure that the product complies with the law, and to protect the individual privacy of your customers. Few people today look kindly on organizations that do not observe their privacy.*

Audit Requirements (15d)

Content *Specification of what the product has to do (usually retain records) to permit the required audit checks.*

Motivation *To build a system that complies with the appropriate audit rules.*

Immunity Requirements (15e)

Content *The requirements for what the product has to do to protect itself from infection by unauthorized or undesirable software programs, such as viruses, worms, malware, spyware and any other undesirable interference.*

Motivation *To build a product that is as secure as possible from malicious interference.*

Cultural Requirements (16a)

Content *This section contains requirements that are specific to the sociological factors that affect the acceptability of the product. If you are developing a product for foreign markets, then these requirements are particularly relevant.*

Motivation *To bring out in the open requirements that are difficult to discover because they are outside the cultural experience of the developers.*

Political Requirements (16b)

Content *This section contains requirements that are specific to the political factors that affect the acceptability of the product.*

Motivation *To understand requirements that sometimes appear irrational.*

Compliance Requirements (17a)

Content *A statement specifying the legal requirements for this system.*

Motivation *To comply with the law so as to avoid later delays, lawsuits, and legal fees.*

Standards Requirements (17b)

Content *A statement specifying applicable standards and referencing detailed standards descriptions. This does not refer to the law of the land—think of it as an internal law imposed by your company.*

Motivation *To comply with standards so as to avoid later delays.*

2.3.2 Requirements in the SatisFactory design process

As illustrated in Figure 6 SatisFactory has adopted an iterative human-centred design approach. Different types of artefacts are used for describing information relevant for the individual stages of the process. For example, user needs and scenarios are used to capture results of the analysis of the context of use, cf. SatisFactory D1.2. And they are used as background for co-creating and illustrating use cases and requirements as well as features for the systems to be developed. (Holbrook 1990, Chin et al. 1997, Glinz 2000, Sutcliffe 2003)

By using the online support presented in section 2.3.3, the authoring of user needs and requirements, with the possibility of authoring of features and other development issues, allows for creating a network of interrelated design artefacts in the interest of achieving design traceability as advocated by ISO 9241, see also (Ramesch and Jarke 2001). The following picture present the Iterative human-centred design approach adopted in SatisFactory following ISO 9241, part 210 (ISO 2010) and the allocation of the appropriate work packages.

Figure 6: Iterative human-centred design approach

In order to ease the formulation of requirements we employ a pre-step to Volere requirements where the so-called *requirements for use* (also known as *user requirements* or *usage requirements*) are formulated. Requirements for use are requirements that are directly following from the context of use. In fact, they are derived from the user needs.

Definition

Requirement for use – A necessary activity a user conducts with the system– describing the activity and not the technical realisation.

Requirements for use have the following characteristics:

- Requirements for use based on user needs in the context of use
- Requirements for use are interpretations of a user need (technology independent)

To support their formulation the scheme presented in Figure 7 should be used.

Figure 7: Syntax for formulating requirements for use

2.3.3 Online support for requirements in SatisFactory

For the creation and management of information elements of a design process, a number of different approaches have been suggested (Stufflebeam et al. 2003, Penna et al. 2003). In the authors experience most tools that go beyond Microsoft Word and Excel have little prospect of being used on a broad basis among a heterogeneous group of partners in international R&D projects. And while MS Word and Excel are certainly adequate for representing a set of user needs or requirements, they have not proven effective in sustainably supporting a continuous and iterative design process.

In the interest of providing other means to reach this objective, Fraunhofer FIT has developed an approach for using the general-purpose web-based ticketing system JIRA² for distributed and collaborative authoring and management of design related information (Easterbrook 1993, Jarke and Pohl 1994).

JIRA uses the issue paradigm which is generally known from bug-tracking and customer-support systems. This paradigm provides a flexible and most importantly light-weight way of creating and managing information items, assigning responsibilities and supporting adapted levels of control for the design process by way of role-based workflows.

The SatisFactory JIRA project space can be found at the following address and is hosted, maintained and supported by Fraunhofer FIT: <https://jira.fit.fraunhofer.de/jira/browse/SAFA/>.

Two general issue types are currently available in the JIRA space of the SatisFactory project.

The first is the "User Need" that supports the activities of the analysis of the context of use that result in the identification of the user needs based on the data gathered during the ethnographic research that is conducted at the pilot sites COMAU, SUNLIGHT and CERTH. The creation dialog for user needs in JIRA is shown in Figure 8.

The second is the "Volere Requirement" that is formed according to the Volere requirements template, also called "Requirements Shell", that is depicted in Figure 3. As already mentioned in subsection 2.3.1.1 the generic Volere requirements template has been slightly adapted to ease the

² <https://de.atlassian.com/software/jira>

prioritization of the requirements and enhance the process of authoring and collaboration. In particular, customer satisfaction and dissatisfaction ratings have been replaced by a more “natural” scheme, the MoSCoW method, and the fields have been classified in “Mandatory” and “Supporting entries” in order to increase usability for the authoring task. Figure 9 and Figure 10 show the two groups of entry fields in the requirements creation dialog. This classification, however, does not mean that “Supporting entries” are not important and thus should not be filled in! In fact, the opposite is the case: The supporting entries “Requirement Type”, “Dependencies” and “Conflicts” are crucial to support of searching, reviewing, planning implementation and generally making sense of the requirements. Thus, they are indispensable for passing the quality control of a requirement.

Project*

Issue Type* ?

Some issue types are unavailable due to incompatible field configuration and/or workflow associations.

Summary*

Description

No file selected.

The maximum file upload size is 10.00 MB.

Create another

Figure 8: Screenshot of the user need creation dialog in SatisFactory

Project*

Issue Type* ?

Some issue types are unavailable due to incompatible field configuration and/or workflow associations.

Mandatory Supporting entries

Summary*

Priority ?

Description

?

Rationale

Why is the requirement considered important or necessary?

Fit Criterion

A quantification of the requirement used to determine whether the requirement is met

Source

From which stakeholder and which event did this requirement emerge?

Attachment No files selected.

The maximum file upload size is 10.00 MB.

Create another

Figure 9: "Mandatory" part of the Volere Requirement creation dialog

Project*

Issue Type* ?

Some issue types are unavailable due to incompatible field configuration and/or workflow associations.

Mandatory Supporting entries

Requirement Type

Dependencies

Other requirements with a change effect

Conflicts

Requirements that contradict this one

Create another

Figure 10: "Supporting entries" part of the Volere Requirement creation dialog

In the “Annex 2 – Requirements template (Volere)” the template adopted for the Satisfactory project is attached.

A state diagram defining possible states of an issue and appropriate transitions between states has been implemented for both types of issues, “User Need” and “Volere Requirement”, in the Satisfactory requirements engineering process. The state diagrams are shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

In particular Figure 11 shows that as soon as a user need has been created it is in an “open” state. After an “open” user need has passed the quality check should be set to “quality check passed” state. The state “duplicate” can be assigned from all states (here the two mentioned above) and means that this user need actually is redundant to another user need, i.e. it duplicates another existing issue. Logic depicted in Figure 12 is the same as for the previous description.

Figure 11: State diagram of issue type “User Need”

Figure 12: State diagram of issue type “Volere Requirement”

3. CONTEXT OF USE ANALYSIS

In this chapter the production processes, as well as the actors and stakeholders considered in the SatisFactory project are analysed. First section gives the main definitions, while the second one introduces details of the considered manufacturing processes with the associated workers involved for each domain.

3.1 PRODUCTION PROCESSES, ACTORS AND STAKEHOLDERS

3.1.1 Production processes

SatisFactory project started the user needs analysis, focusing on the areas of expertise of the end-user partners composing the consortium. Such processes cover a wide range of European industrial sectors. They refer in particular to the discrete manufacturing, represented by the application in Automotive & Machining, where COMAU provides his expertise, by the Batteries Manufacturing, led by SunLight and, finally, the Chemical Process Industry, coordinated by CERTH.

Main goal of the SatisFactory Project is the improvement of the Process Operator Workplace, however to deeply analyse such enhancement it is compulsory to take into consideration also the coordinating functions as well as the design and engineering roles. The three main layers afore mentioned are depicted in the following pyramid.

Figure 13: End-users test-beds reference model

3.1.2 Actors and Stakeholders

In the Satisfactory Project, the term “Actors” identify all specific roles involved in the manufacturing process, while all supporting design and engineering roles, as well as connected staff functions are named “Stakeholders”. More precisely the Project will focus and develop applications for the “Actors” such as Process Operators, and their first management level (i.e. Team Leaders, Foremen and Coordinators). Additional figures that will be considered in SatisFactory, are the roles devoted to design and engineering activities of the workplaces, as well as ergonomics validations.

Figure 14: Categorization of Actors and Stakeholders

The previously described model can be extended, considering more roles in the companies, and their supply chains, e.g. tier 1 suppliers. These figures have been included in the following representation, and they will be part of the next iterations of the requirements engineering process.

Figure 15: Categorization of Internal Stakeholders and Connected Stakeholders

A preliminary analysis of the legislation , related to safety and ergonomics in the workplace has been performed by the end-users and technological partners. The result is attached in "Annex 3 – Legislation review" and "Annex 4 – Workplaces ergonomics".

3.2 *DESCRIPTION OF THE CONTEXT OF USE*

Hereafter the processes and related actors & stakeholders for each of the three end-user scenarios are described. Moreover some highlights of the maintenance actors are presented.

3.2.1 *COMAU - Automotive discrete manufacturing*

3.2.1.1 *Process*

COMAU has taken into consideration 3 specific manufacturing processes that have key roles in its core business. In particular the first one is developed within the Robotics Business Unit and is focused on the robot hollow wrist assembly. The second and the third processes consider two applications of the Body Welding business unit, more precisely the welding guns assembly process and the welding lines assembly are analysed.

- **Robotics - Hollow wrist assembly**

Used in welding applications, hollow wrist robots or robots with cabling integrated through the arm, have become a staple in automated welding systems. Designed with the cables integrated in the arm of the robot, they are easy to install into a new or existing cell, increase productivity and product quality, and reduce wear and tear on expensive cables.

Main advantages are respectively Easy to program/simulate, Larger work envelope, Higher robot density, Greater accessibility and Simplified tooling.

COMAU produces different models of robots with hollow wrist with different sizes and payloads according to the customers' needs (patented solution EP1970171A1).

In the pictures below is represented a Smart5 NJ4-90, an hollow wrist robot with a payload of 90 kg, used mainly for welding applications in the automotive industry and a schema of the hollow wrist.

Figure 16: COMAU Smart5 NJ4-90 hollow wrist robot

Figure 17: COMAU robot hollow wrist

The mechanical assembly of these robots is done internally in COMAU completely by operators and it is composed by a specific sequence of operations that must be followed accurately in order to guarantee the performances and high level of reliability that characterized COMAU products.

In particular the assembly process includes operations such as cleaning of the mechanical parts coming from foundry/machining, gears and spacers assembly, sealing and grease filling, test of tolerances & mechanical couplings and finally marking electrical motors & wiring assembly.

- **Body Welding – Welding guns assembly**

Resistive spot welding is a process in which contacting metal surfaces are joined by the heat obtained from resistance to electric current. Work-pieces are held together under pressure exerted by electrodes. The process uses two shaped copper alloy electrodes to concentrate welding current into a small "spot" and to simultaneously clamp the sheets together. Forcing a large current through the spot will melt the metal and form the weld. The attractive feature of spot welding is that a lot of energy can be delivered to the spot in a very short time.

COMAU developed a Spot Welding Guns family, specifically developed for the automotive sector. These products are characterized by simplicity and modularity. Three standard chassis provide a robust and compact solution; 100% of typical car body shop requirements are satisfied with this versatile product. Main features are:

- Robust and compact
- COMAU Servo actuator
- COMAU transformer (MFDC)
- Equalisation through robot compensation
- No external cables
- RobCAD Simulation effectively 100%
- Fireproof(ABS VH-0800E)cover protects from spatter/contamination

Following a picture of a typical welding gun integrated with a robot system and a mechanical drawing of a welding gun are provided.

Figure 18: COMAU Smart5 NJ4-90 with COMAU Compact welding gun

Figure 19: COMAU Compact welding gun

COMAU welding gun assembly process involves the preparation of the mechanical structure of the body with the transformer, followed by the integration of the arms with the copper tips holders and the linear motor. Finally the wiring and piping complete the installation.

The mechanical assembly is followed by a testing and certification that include a fine tuning of the welding parameters.

- **Body Welding - Welding lines assembly**

One of the main stages of the car production is the assembly and welding of the car body. This process is performed on robotized production lines, where automated clamps and fixtures hold the metal parts in position while robots perform welding operations.

COMAU is a global leader in advanced production systems for vehicle full body, components manufacturing, as well as turnkey body shops.

One of the main components of these manufacturing lines are the reference tools including clamps and fixtures, needed to give the elements the proper geometry and characteristics of the subsystems of the whole car body that has to be manufactured.

Following a picture of a body welding line is provided, as well as an example of a reference gate that holds a body-side in position during welding operations.

Figure 20: COMAU body-welding line

Figure 21: COMAU body-side fixtures

One of the main phases of COMAU body-welding lines assembly process is the construction of the reference structures that hold the sheet-metal parts. These operations are performed by the installation of clamps and fixtures on the mechanical frame, followed by fluidics piping to connect compressed air and electrical wiring of the mechatronics devices. These operations are done following detailed mechanical and electrical drawings provided by the engineering department. The mechanical and electrical assembly is followed by a testing and certification that include a fine tuning of the clamping system and I/O testing.

3.2.1.2 **Actors & Stakeholders**

In COMAU use-cases three different groups of resources have been considered. Starting from the design & engineering to the process execution is it possible to identify the Design & Ergonomics Engineer, the Process Operator, and his responsible, the Technical Leader.

- **Process Operator**

The Process Operator is a mechatronics worker, responsible for the construction of machinery and production systems, from the assembly of single components to the full integrated system, including the following tasks:

- mechanical assembly
- electrical wiring
- fluidics piping
- preliminary and final testing
- troubleshooting
- support to power-up and final delivery to customer (commissioning)

These operations are performed in a team and under the supervision of the Technical Leader.

Figure 22: Process Operators during piping installation on a robot arm

- **Technical Leader**

The Technical Leader is responsible for coordinating the resources (i.e. Process Operators) needed to carry out a specific project, under constraints of customer's specifications, internal resources availability, project timeline, budget. He must guarantee the requested technical performances from the early stages of preliminary design, to the detailed design of machines and manufacturing systems, until the final customer's acceptance, with the support of project manager. He has the responsibility for:

- technical design of machines and lines with dedicated team
- design team coordination
- external suppliers management
- ensuring the project progress according to milestones
- interfacing with workers employed in actual building of machinery in the shop floor.

- **Design & Ergonomics Engineer**

The Design & Ergonomics Engineer is responsible for detailed design of the technical solutions needed to complete a specific customer's project, under the coordination of the Technical Leader. He must guarantee, within his area of expertise, the full compliance of the project with the expected requirements, managing all aspects related to:

- layout of machines
- mechanical design
- electrical/software/hydraulic design
- ergonomics and safety issues
- preparation of drawings and diagrams for machinery and accessory parts construction.

3.2.2 CERTH/CPERI – Chemical continuous process

3.2.2.1 Significant infrastructure/Technical Equipment/Products/Services

CERTH/CPERI has a wide range of industrial automation systems and industrial software platforms. The automated systems are used for process control and remote monitoring (SCADA, DCS, PLC based). Also Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition Systems (SCADA) for chemical and energy production processes are in operation with respective middleware software, with OPC connectivity. CERTH/CPERI has developed and supports a wide multi-sensorial network of heterogeneous distributed systems (indicative industrial protocols: CANBus, Profibus, EtherCat, RS485).

Within the project, CERTH/CPERI will utilize its industrial automation infrastructure for the deployment of the integrated Reference Architecture Platform to CERTH/CPERI's process plants where the Industrial Lab cases will take place and selected shop-floor processes will be used as a test bed for SatisFactory products and solutions.

CERTH/CPERI's infrastructure consists of numerous experimental industrial process systems where information is propagated through a network backbone that facilitates data exchange from and to the input/output field of respective units. Each unit has sensors that acquire various signals which

are distributed in a wide area and are connected using industrial networks. The monitoring and control is performed in real time and cover actions and events that take place throughout the life cycle of the information, starting from the encoding at the physical layer to the knowledge sharing to the end user. In order to provide a uniform way of communication at the application layer between the various sources and sinks of data, OPC-based interfaces are developed and deployed at each individual process unit.

Figure 23: Partial overview of CERTH/CPERIs shop floor and plants

Figure 24: CERTH/CPERIs Monitoring and control HMIs

- **Pilot Plant 1 –Batch process**

A combined hydroprocessing pilot-plant, fractionation unit, auto-clave reactor, fuel accelerated aging unit, as well as analytical instruments for fuel quality control will be used as one of the Use Case of SatisFactory. Among the related infrastructure, there are both continuous and batch process units which are at presented operated and monitored online. As each unit has different operating and safety challenges, two of them will be used as case studies in this project, the small hydroprocessing pilot plant (VB01) as a continuous process unit and the vacuum fractionation unit (HyDis) as a batch process unit. The VB01 continuous hydroprocessing pilot plant consists of a feed system, a single-reactor system and a product separation system. The feed system effectively maintains constant feed quality and H₂-to-oil ratio via a liquid feed pump and a gas flow controller. The reactor system consists of a single fixed-bed reactor with six independent heating zones, which sustain the desired temperature profile within the reactor. The reactor product passes through the product separation system, where it is first cooled via a cooling zone and then flashed via a High Pressure Low Temperature (HPLT) separator. It should also be noted that both feeds and products

(gas and liquid) will be analysed within the CERTH/CPERI analytic laboratory equipped with state-of-the-art analytical instruments capable for all key fuel analysis. The operation of VB01 is enabled by a SCADA system that employs the total of 38 process variables associated with the unit via 17 control loops that are intended to maintain stable temperature, pressure, and flow rate within the reactor and feed/product lines.

Figure 25: Process Overview

One of the main operating challenges of the VB01 process unit is the varying operating conditions and feedstock types that are required when testing different feedstock and technologies. In particular, the system pressure may vary from 500 to 2000 psig, and the reactor temperature from 250 to 380°C. Moreover, feedstock that have been already utilized have different flow and composition characteristics. The wide operating window dictates the utilization of online and historical data as a database of local operating regions that will enable stable operation via setting the total of 17 control loops associated with it.

- **Pilot Plant 2 – Continuous Process**

A pilot plant that will be used for SatisFactory project is the SynGas unit of CERTH/CPERI-LPSDI. This pilot plant has been used for steam reforming and partial oxidation of methane and aqueous mixtures of hydrocarbons such as methanol and bio-oil. Catalytic partial oxidation of Methane can be an attractive process for converting natural gas to synthesis gas (SYNGAS), because it gives high methane conversions (over 90% per pass) combined with high selectivity to carbon monoxide. The unit supports a spout bed type reactor and a fixed bed reactor used alternatively for preliminary activity measurements. The pilot plant is fully automated and intuitive HMIs represent the alternative flow sheet of either reactor. The pilot plant unit is fully automated using a supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system. All system components (pumps, heaters, valves and so forth) are controlled by on/off commands or by pre-programmed start-up procedures. A remote monitoring system has been developed in order to provide real-time information regarding the state of the plant, as well as, trending features related to the evolution of the experiment runs. Among the objectives of the automation system, is the ability of the user to monitor the plant by utilizing a standard web browser base application and a secure information exchange framework.

Figure 26: Process Flow diagram of the Continuous Pilot Plant

- **Infrastructure related components**

Both pilot plants produce each day real-time data stored in repositories that provide a significant amount of information currently analysed using conventional tools while the decision making relies on information which is compiled in a manual manner by the process operators and the process supervisors. Besides the collection, analysis and deployment of automated actions, the aforementioned infrastructure is equipped with data visualization tools combined with content aware functions using diagnosis and alarm triggering tools. The user interacts with the devices, the sensors and the actuators through a set of user-friendly human machine interfaces (HMI) that provide the basis for the decision making process in real-time. Furthermore, the data can be accessed by local or remote information points and can be managed by supervisory functions. Thus, the operators can intuitively understand the status and the various conditions of the process equipment and respond accordingly upon demand. The aforementioned infrastructure is developed using a set of adaptive user interfaces combined with flexible sensor topologies that are able to tackle the heterogeneity of the various devices which are present in a smart factory.

The pilot plants are fully automated and controlled by a SCADA system with intuitive HMIs that represent the alternative flow sheet of either reactor. All system components (pumps, heaters, valves and so forth) are controlled by on/off commands or by pre-programmed start-up procedures. A remote monitoring system is present that provides real-time information regarding the state of the plant, as well as, trending features related to the evolution of the experiment runs. The SCADA system allows the operators to monitor the plant by utilizing a standard web browser based application and a secure information exchange framework.

Figure 27: Knowledge sharing from the signal data to actionable knowledge

3.2.2.2 *Actors & stakeholders*

- **Floor manager**

The floor manager has the general supervision on the workflow of the shop floor. He also makes integration decision support for allocation of resources at existing processes. He/she must have good knowledge on chemical processes, administrative skills and knowledge on management of human resources.

- **Process supervisor**

The process supervisor is responsible for the general operation of a pilot plant. He/she shares information with all involved actors about daily experiments and processes the data from the field and the laboratory analysis. He/she also schedules new constructions or system revamps. He/she must have administrative skills, experience on chemical processes, excellent knowledge of the operation of the pilot plant and good knowledge on using process monitoring systems.

- **Maintenance manager**

The maintenance manager is responsible of organising scheduled tasks on the shop floor. He/she is also involved on new constructions or system revamps scheduling and is informed about existing work progress and involvement of the technical team. He/she must have collaboration skills and automation, electrical and mechanical knowledge.

- **Maintenance supervisor**

The maintenance supervisor is responsible to coordinate the members of the technical team. He/she has collaboration with the maintenance manager, the process supervisors and the technical team in order to organize the scheduled and sudden actions. He/she must be in place to take immediate decisions when is needed. His/her collaboration with other stakeholders must be very good. Human resources management and automation, electrical and mechanical knowledge are mandatory.

- **Process technician**

The main task of process technicians is to support and maintain the operation of the pilot plants. He must be able to use various machine shop tools and he must have good knowledge of mechanical design software.

- **Control, automation, IT technician**

The maintenance of IT and automation structures is the main concern of this category of actors. They are also involved in new constructions and revamps. Experience on SCADA and automation software as well as IT infrastructure knowledge are required for this position.

- **Electrical technician**

Electrical technicians support the operation of pilot plants. They are involved in new constructions and revamps and preserve information related to performed procedures. They must have good knowledge and experience on high and low voltage electrical systems and must be able to understand electrical schematics and manuals.

- **Process operator**

Process operators perform daily actions regarding the operation of pilot plants. They report about malfunctions of abnormal behaviour of the operation and organise raw materials for the experiments. They have collaboration with process supervisors and with the members of the technical team.

3.2.3 *SUNLIGHT – Batteries discrete manufacturing*

3.2.3.1 *Process*

Sunlight will involve three manufacturing processes related with three different production lines. The first one is the jar formation process which is the last stage of the PzS batteries production line. The second one is Motive power (traction) batteries assembly line and third one is the manual assembly line of the OPzS and OpzV batteries.

- **Jar Formation Process**

The initial formation charge of a lead-acid battery, whether in the form of plates or as an already assembled battery, is quite a complex bundle of chemical reactions. It is important to know in principle about the most important parameters controlling this process in order to achieve good reproducible results with reasonable efforts.

Jar formation is applied to already assembled batteries. The formation process for the batteries cells begins with the filling process. The time gap between electrolyte filling and the initiation of the formation process must be considered very carefully. If batteries are put into formation immediately after filling, a significant amount of acid may remain unreacted. There are several Formation algorithms and profiles that can be applied. Several conditions must be considered for applying the most proper formation profile.

Figure 28: Jar formation

- **Motive power (Traction) battery assembly**

Sunlight Motive power batteries can cover all types of motive power needs, from light duty single-shift operation to heavy duty multi-shift operations, and are suitable for all industrial electric forklift types, such as counterbalanced, narrow aisle and hand trucks.

The Motive Power battery assembly procedure includes the following stages:

- Cells fitting into metal tray
- Inspection level electrolyte
- Battery cleaning
- Connectors fitting

- Inspection bolts and voltage
- Labels fitting
- Advisories & appurtenances fitting
- Palletizing & packing with nylon

Figure 29: Sunlight Motive Power Battery

Figure 30: Sunlight Motive Power Battery Assembly line

- **OPzS and OPzV battery manual assembly**

OPzS and OPzV batteries are characterized by their long life span, durability under cyclic use conditions as well as for their low maintenance requirements, providing you a cost effective energy solution. Their robust construction, the high quality raw materials used for their production in addition to their optimum design - according to DIN international standards, enhance their capacity and performance.

OPzS and OPzV batteries are assembled manually. The assembly production line includes the following processes:

- Plate cropping and brushing
- Block stacking
- Poles and strap welding
- Battery cell assembly
- Lid gluing
- Electrolyte filling
- Battery Activation
- Cleaning
- Labelling
- Packing

Figure 31: OPzS & OPzV Manual Assembly line

Actors & stakeholders

- **Operators**

Operators are operating the machines or assembling batteries on the shop floor. They are monitoring the production process and carrying out basic testing and quality checks. They are cleaning and maintaining work areas and machinery. They may also supervise Trainees during the working day.

- **Trainees**

Trainees are not experienced operators who have been working at a factory's workplace less than six months and thus are getting trained.

- **Foreman or Operations Supervisor**

Operations Supervisors are highly experienced workers with a very good knowledge of the machines and good understanding of the work processes. They are responsible for training of new workers (Trainees). They spend about 90% of their working time on the shop floor. Their main responsibilities are Coordinate daily production floor activities and delegate assignments to production personnel.

- **Mechanical Technicians and Electricians**

Mechanical Technicians and Electricians are part of the Technical team and are responsible for new installations, Troubleshooting and maintenance of the infrastructure.

Installing new machinery or equipment, the Mechanical technicians are responsible for the mechanical installations and assembly of the mechanical part. The Electricians are responsible for the cabling and all the necessary electrical and electronic connections that will make the machine workable.

- **Production Plant Manager**

The Production Plant Manager controls and coordinates the manufacturing processes. He maintain optimum operation by assigning workers, keeping work and production schedules, collecting and looking through data to find places of waste or places of improvement, keep an eye on worker safety and plant safety.

- **Production Planner**

Production Planner plans and prepares production schedules for manufacture of the products: Draws up master schedule to establish sequence and lead time of each operation to meet shipping dates according to sales forecasts or customer orders.

- **Production Supervisors**

Production Supervisor completes production plan by scheduling and assigning personnel, accomplishing work results, establishing priorities, monitoring progress, revising schedules, resolving problem, reporting results of the processing flow on shift production summaries.

- **Maintenance Manager**

Maintenance manager primary responsibilities are management, maintenance and construction of manufacturing facilities, associated infrastructure and manufacturing equipment. He manages the

staff, processes and activities for maintaining all plant machinery to ensure safe, continual and efficient operation.

3.2.4 ATLANTIS – Maintenance operations

3.2.4.1 Process

Atlantis develops and implements solutions in the field of electromechanical equipment maintenance and industrial production.

In the SatisFactory project main effort of Atlantis will be devoted to the development and implementation of innovative applications for maintenance purposes, in order to be applied to the industrial sectors.

3.2.4.2 Actors & stakeholders

- **Maintenance Manager**

The Maintenance Manager directs and manages the plant maintenance staff, programs and processes, typically under direction of the plant operations manager or production manager, in order to ensure safe, timely and efficient operation of all plant machinery and equipment. He plans the procedure to be applied on the shop-floor, defines and develops maintenance strategies, policies and criteria for performance, according to the company strategies. He define the organizational model of maintenance, the processes and tools to support the tasks. He ensures the levels of availability, reliability, maintainability, supportability, safety and quality required for the entire useful life of assets, while staying within the budget.

- **Maintenance Supervisor**

The Maintenance Supervisor is the connection between the management and the actual performance of the tasks. He is directly responsible for overseeing the efforts of maintenance workers who install, repair or service property or machinery. He plans the maintenance tasks within his area of responsibility. He organizes, manages and develops the maintenance resources: personnel, materials and equipment; while ensuring compliance with regulations and procedures related to safety, health and environment. He participates in the technical aspects of contracts and procurement process and manage the performance of the contractors and communicates to all necessary partners like staff, contractors, customers and suppliers.

- **Maintenance Coordinator**

In some plants, there is a Maintenance Coordinator, who acts under the Maintenance Manager (or Supervisor, depending on the size of the plant), in terms of organizing and coordinating the maintenance tasks. This role is more 'administrative', helping communicating tasks from the Supervisor to the Technicians.

- **Maintenance Technician**

The Maintenance Technician is the person that receives directions and has the technical knowledge and skills to implement the tasks assigned to him by the Supervisor (or Manager, if there is no Supervisor) He performs or ensures proper execution according to rules and procedures relating to safety, health and environmental protection. He acts promptly in case of failure or malfunction, ensuring the effectiveness of the restoration. He ensures the availability of materials, tools and equipment necessary for the execution of maintenance tasks. He is the one using or ensuring the usage of ICT systems.

4. END-USERS REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

This chapter briefly introduces the process adopted to collect the user requirements, conducted through face-to-face interviews in the premises of the three considered industrial sectors: automotive machinery, battery production and chemical process. Following an analysis of these interviews is presented.

4.1 REQUIREMENTS COLLECTION PROCESS

SatisFactory end-users have been actively involved in the requirements collection. A total of 41 interviews has been performed, 18 to CERTH resources, 15 of them to Comau employees, and finally 8 to Sunlight personnel.

The questionnaire is composed by 40 queries organized in eight sections, respectively:

- Section 1 – Company general information, containing general questions regarding the organization figures;
- Section 2 – Actor/Stakeholder general information, which includes requests about experience, know-how and role of the interviewed person;
- Section 3 – Activities/Work description, asking details about involved process and workplace;
- Section 4 – Employees turnover, with requests on job recruiting process;
- Section 5 – Training received , regarding the way the actual job was learned and training needs;
- Section 6 – Procedures and guidelines applied (plus IT support), to collect information on the IT enabling environment to be used at workplace level and documents/procedures accessed;
- Section 7 – Working scenario improvement, containing questions about possible enhancements of the working environment;
- Section 8 – Other suggestions

The questionnaire template is attached to this document as "*Annex 1 – Interview notes and template*".

Each interview lasted approximately 1 hour and provided good feedbacks and suggestions for the SatisFactory Project developments. Generally, the interviewed people answered to all the questions: only sometimes problems of confidentiality or of lack of information arise. Due to privacy

company rules and the distribution level of this document, only aggregated data at use-case level will be presented. In "Annex 5 – Informed Consent For Interviews" a consent letter form is presented. In the following sections the main achievements from the interview process are described for the three industrial sectors considered.

4.2 REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

4.2.1 COMAU - Automotive discrete manufacturing

The personnel interviewed by COMAU have been selected according to three different criteria:

- Application environment (Robot wrist assembly, Welding guns assembly, Welding lines assembly);
- Company role (Process operator, Team leader, Design & ergonomics engineer);
- Years of experience in the role .

In order to proceed with the collection of contributions from the experts, a formal procedure of authorization requests has been followed. COMAU management was involved to validate the interview process, in particular, the Engineering and Quality Vice-President, the Human Resources office, the Legal office and the Manufacturing responsible.

For confidentiality and privacy reasons only aggregated data will be presented in the following.

At the end of the COMAU interviews round a total of 15 experts was interviewed. All interviews have been performed face-to-face in COMAU meeting rooms or directly in shop-floor environment. Final percentage of answered question was about 95,2%.

Out of the 15 interviewed persons, 4 experts belong to the Robotics area and in particular to the robot wrist assembly, 5 specialists come from the body welding area and specifically from the welding gun assembly area; finally 6 experts belong to the body welding lines assembly operations.

Considering their role in COMAU, the 15 interviewed are clustered as 7 Process operators, 4 Technical leaders and 4 Design & ergonomics engineers, as represented in the following diagram.

Figure 32: COMAU stakeholders applications & roles

A different parameter used to classify the actors was regarding their education level. The results are presented in the figure below. It is possible to see that the three figures selected (Opertors, Technical Leaders, Designers) well reflect on the education degree, with 1 third that has vocational degree, 1 third Bachelor and 1 third Master degree.

Figure 33: COMAU actors and stakeholders' education level

Considering the experience in the role, 5 interviewed have till 5 years of knowledge, 6 are in the range between 5 to 20 years, and finally, 4 have more than 20 years of experience.

Figure 34: COMAU stakeholders years of experience in the role

With respect to the question 2.5 of the questionnaire: "Which are your main areas of expertise?"

The following result, presented in the figure below, has been achieved: main competence areas are in the mechanics, followed by electrical & software, and project & process management.

Figure 35: COMAU Technological areas of expertise

Another interesting point raised up from the questionnaires results is how COMAU employees came to their actual working position. As depicted in the picture below, most of the actors came internally from different FIAT Group companies. The other different entries like University, stages, suppliers, other employees and labor office are well balanced

Figure 36: How COMAU actors came to this job

With respect to the safety issues, that play a key role in the manufacturing shop-floor, and in the workplace, question 3.5 of the questionnaire: “Do you use any specific safety device?” aimed to quantify the usage of personal protective equipment by the experts. All the in 15 interviewed use foot/leg protections (i.e. Safety shoes) when they are in the shop-floor, while respectively 10 and 9 use hand and eye protections (safety gloves and safety glasses). Finally only 4 perform activities requiring body protections (safety belts).

Figure 37: Personal Protective Equipment (OSHA classification)

The graph presented in the figure above, is strictly connected to the fact that quite all the interviewed actors spend some of the working-time in the manufacturing shop-floor. This is confirmed by the picture below.

Figure 38: COMAU actors' workplace

With reference to “Section 4 – Employees turnover” and in particular to question “How many years do you think people stay in the company on average?”, the analysis highlights that more than 70% of the interviewed feels that the team in which they operate has a low turnover. This is represented in the following figure.

Figure 39: Personnel Turnover

With reference to Section 5, and more precisely to question “How would you train someone to do your job? Or, how would you have wished to be trained?”, the 47% of the interviewed employees prefers a formal training including training on the job, the 40% prefers a formal training and the remaining 13% prefers a more direct approach with only training on the job.

It is interesting to remark that process operators, that normally receive only training on the job would like to receive also formal trainings with more theoretical concepts.

Figure 40: Personnel wished training

Final question related to the degree of satisfaction of the actual workplace for the interviewed experts. It was asked them to provide a value between 1 and 10 where 1 was the least satisfaction level and 10 was the maximum. The 15 answers obtained were in the range 5 to 9, thus in order to simplify the reading, they have been clustered in 4 groups, respectively 5-6 (3 answers), 7 (5 answers), 8 (6 answers) and, finally 9 (1 answer). The following diagram shows the percentages of these results.

Figure 41: Overall Workplace satisfaction degree

4.2.2 CERTH – Chemical continuous process

These results refer to the eighteen (18) actors that were interviewed within CERTH. The criteria that used for the selection of the employees to be interviewed based on the fact that we should choose actors from all the categories we have. Thus, we chose:

- 6 process operators (from 2 pilot plants)
- 9 technicians (4 Automation / IT technicians, 3 process technicians and 2 electrical technicians)
- 3 supervisors (floor manager, process supervisor, maintenance supervisor)

The following diagram shows the above categories:

Figure 42: CERTH actors' categories

The interview procedure carried out with no problems. Actors showed great interest and were willing to answer most of the questions because they thought it is an opportunity to improve several problems regarding their daily actions.

We separate actors considering their experience in their roles and we found that the majority (9 actors) is between 5 to 20 years, 5 of the actors have 5 and less years of experience and 4 of them are very experienced, with more than 20 years at their jobs. The following diagram presents these results.

Figure 43: CERTH actors' years of experience

Another way to separate actors was regarding their education level. The results are presented in the above figure. We can point out that only 6% of the actors have vocational education, in contrast with a 55% with masters or PhD degree. This means that most of CERTH's employees are highly educated.

Figure 44: CERTH actors' education level

Trying to find out the areas of expertise of the actors (question 2.5 of the questionnaire), we created the next figure. The main competence areas seem to be the pilot plant operation and the electrical and automation areas. This seems reasonable since most of the interviewed actors were process operators or technicians. Biofuels and renewable energy area follows, which is also reasonable because of the areas that CERTH deals with.

Figure 45: CERTH actors' areas of expertise

Another very interesting point that came out of the results of the questionnaires is how CERTH actors came to their current job. As we can see at the next figure, most of the actors came as students (internship or bachelor thesis) first and after that they were hired as employees. This means that CERTH has a very good collaboration with education institutes (universities, technological schools) and they try to invest on people who begin their careers and have fresh ideas and lot of energy.

Figure 46: How CERTH actors came to this job

Referring to the 3.2 question of the questionnaire, we can see where actors spend their working hours. From the eighteen employees that were interviewed, 100% of them answered that spends some time at the shop floor. We can also see that all actors have their own office. The other places, like the machine shop or the laboratories, are used from some of the actors depending from their activities.

Figure 47: CERTH actors' workplace

Question 3.5 of the questionnaire refers to safety equipment that is used at CERTH facilities. Actors' safety has a critical role at CERTH because working conditions inside the shop floor area are dangerous and unhealthy. All actors, depending on their role, must use safety equipment in order not to expose themselves into any danger. As we can see at the next figure, most of the actors use safety glasses, working apron and safety gloves. Some of them use safety masks, while others use safety shoes and helmet.

Figure 48: CERTH actors' safety equipment usage

With reference to "Section 4 – Employees turnover" of the questionnaire and in particular to question "How many years do you think people stay in the company on average?", it seems clearly that actors of CERTH are satisfied from their jobs. Almost 80% of the actors stay at this job more than 10 years, with almost half of them for all their careers and only about 15% stay less than a decade.

Figure 49: CERTH actors' turnover

With reference to "Section 5" and more precisely to question "How would you train someone to do your job? Or, how would you have wished to be trained?" the results that are presented at the next figure are very interesting. Most supervisors and process operators believe that theoretical training must be the first issue and practice must follow. In the contrary, most of the technicians would train a new employee by having him all day along them showing how actions must be performed.

Another issue we can point from the diagram is that some of the technicians and the process operators were very satisfied with their training and they would perform the same to a new colleague.

Figure 50: CERTH actors' wished training

The result from "Section 4" (Figure 51) about actor's turnover is being verified from the answers at question 7.5, which was asking from actors to evaluate their workplace. 72% of the actors rated with 8 or higher (from 1-10, 10 being the best) the workspace at CERTH which means that they think it is quite good.

Figure 51: CERTH actors' overall workplace satisfaction degree

4.2.3 SUNLIGHT – Batteries discrete manufacturing

Six (6) actors have been interviewed within Systems Sunlight. The employees have been chosen from different departments and they have been classified as following:

- 1 operator (from the maintenance department)
- 1 foreman (from the Jar formation department)
- 2 production supervisors (battery production, formation department)
- 1 factory production manager
- 1 maintenance manager

The results of the interviews presented in the following diagrams:

Figure 52: Sunlight actors' categories

The interviews have been performed smoothly. The actors didn't hesitate to answer to any question. Most of them provide us a lot of information by having with us an open discussion.

Some of the actors are very experienced while some others are new in the company. No one has an experience of more than 20 years. Three of them have less than 5 years and the rest of the actors have an experience between 5 and 20 years. The following diagram presents the results:

Figure 53: Sunlight actors' years of experience

All the actors that have been interviewed have technical education. All of them are involved with mechanics and some of them with electrical, IT technology and automation.

Two thirds of the interviewers have a bachelor degree while half of them have also a master degree. The rest of the actors have technical education.

Figure 54: Sunlight actors' education

Figure 55: Sunlight actors' areas of expertise

Actors have been asked how did they came to work in Sunlight. It is very important that most of them have been suggested or informed by others. This denotes that people (working in Sunlight or not) have a good opinion about the company and they can easily advise others to work in Sunlight. A significant presence answered that they found the job through Networking.

Figure 56: How Sunlight actors' found this job

Actors have been also asked to describe where their workplace is. Most of them have answered that they work both in the shop floor and the office. Some of them are working only in office. Technicians can be in any place in the factory since that they maintain all the machinery and the equipment.

Figure 57: SUNLIGHT actors' workplace

Sunlight is a chemical factory and the use of safety equipment within the several shop floors is mandatory. Factory personnel are well trained and aware of the relevant safety procedures. This is also confirmed by the diagram shown below, where the use of safety equipment such as Uniforms, Glasses, gloves, safety shoes and safety masks, is reported:

Figure 58: Sunlight actors' safety equipment usage

Sunlight actors seem to be satisfied from their jobs because in the question: "How many years do you think people stay in the company on average?", most of them answered that they stay for more than 7 years.

Figure 59: Sunlight actors' turnover

By analysing the answers to the question "How would you train someone to do your job? Or, how would you have wished to be trained?" the results shows that most of them prefer theoretical training together with practical training in the production line.

Figure 60: Sunlight actors' wished training

The actors were asking also to evaluate their workplace. The result shows that they are satisfied since that 83% rated the workplace with 7 and 17% with 8.

Figure 61: Sunlight overall workplace satisfaction degree

5. KEY TOPICS AND REQUIREMENTS

After the analysis of all interviews conducted by the three end-users of the SatisFactory consortium and preliminary brainstorming performed by the four technology partners, an initial Volere requirements database has been filled.

This chapter presents in the first section an example of the key topics derived from industrial partners interviews, while in the second part an extract of the eighty-three (83) requirements contained in the Jira database is shown.

These project needs messages will be subject of further improvements, focusing in particular the adherence to project scope, duplications, priorities management and implementation phases. The results of this enhancement process will be reported in the new releases of the present Deliverable, expected by project month M14 and M26.

5.1 END-USERS KEY TOPICS

This section describes the key topics that represent the synthesis of the end-user needs, derived from the interview process performed in collaboration with personnel coming respectively from the three end-users environments: discrete manufacturing in automotive for COMAU, discrete manufacturing for batteries for SUNLIGHT and continuous process in chemical applications in CERTH labs. Due to privacy issues, only aggregated data is presented in the following sections.

This preliminary analysis allowed to identify the user-requirement areas that will serve as basis for the future SatisFactory implementations. This study has been conducted considering the benefits and improvement areas, as well as the potential weakness and attention fields.

5.1.1 Key topics from Comau interview process

This section summarizes the key topics highlighted during the interview process conducted in Comau. As described below many important messages refer to user needs as well as mandatory and nice to have requirements that could improve the manufacturing operations and the workplace organization, that will lead to an improved worker satisfaction. Some messages refer to potential concerns and areas of attention that must be considered during the project developments.

5.1.1.1 Benefits and improvement areas

1. IT HW/SW platforms provide a good support, to improve the operators access to engineering and manufacturing information and documents
2. IT offers an enabling technology to implement remote functionalities such as production support and remote maintenance
3. Innovative sensing and actuating technologies (IoT) offer a good basis for ergonomics parameters real-time monitoring of human operators (e.g.

accelerations, number of repetitive operations performed, strength required in specific operations, etc.)

4. Safety in the shop-floor can be improved by means of innovative sensing, with safety devices wearing verifications through RFIDs or WSN applications
5. A good support is offered by the innovative sensing on the activities planning, coordinating the resources in order to balance the daily workloads among a team of workers, e.g. planning heavy activities in the first part of the day and light ones in the last part of the shift
6. IT architecture provides an innovative training environment that allows multimedia training procedures and sessions
7. Some procedures require the use of both hands. In this case the use of other senses could be a good alternative. An example could be vocal guides
8. Workloads require that operators replace colleagues in their activities. They must have clear in mind the right Sequence of Operations, so an online guide that reminds the correct steps could avoid mistakes
9. The application of terminals that guide the operators during the production process could lead to assisted production processes that generate automatically reports and checklists according to the operations performed
10. The integration of all devices, like power tools, measuring systems (laser level), etc. could lead to the establishment of a common database where all production data could be managed
11. Manufacturing IT platforms should support planners to assign lighter workloads to elderly/handicapped employees

5.1.1.2 ***Potential weakness and attention areas***

1. Introducing additional IT platform to guide the operators in their daily work activities could represent a potential risk of increasing their normal workload
2. A potential risk of limiting operators privacy is represented by the additional number of cameras and sensors that can track the activities and the time required to perform them
3. New IT environment shall be user-friendly
4. The introduction of new devices in addition to the existing ones means also the addition of activities for their maintenance
5. The introduction of new terminals could lead to the introduction of new training in order to let the people work with these new devices
6. For young people the addition of IT technology, could be interesting, while for more aged persons, could create problems

5.1.2 Key topics from CERTH/CPERI interview process

According to the most significant information gathered from the CERTH actors' interviews, the following list of key topics has been identified:

1. In general, all actors are satisfied with their work and they find it rather interesting
2. A lot of CERTH workers have spent most of their career years at this job so far. In general, people stay many years in this job
3. Almost everyone would recommend his/her friends/children to do the same work
4. Relationships and collaboration between workers are very good
5. Actors who are working most of their time at an office have better working conditions from those who spend more time at the shop floor
6. There is a big need for safety due to the nature of daily activities, therefore all workers use safety measures and would like to be informed about the incidents and the potential situations that might be present at the shop floor
7. There is some flexibility on how each worker manages his working time. It would be beneficial to have an electronic system for the tracking of the activities that will be updated dynamically and accessible to every employee
8. There are written procedures for some of the activities, but they should be more that what actually is available
9. Most of the employees receive many kinds of training regarding their working sections, but they feel the need of continuous training sessions. The field that CERTH is working on is very demanding and employees must always be aware for novel technologies
10. Fire and gas alarms are incidents that can occur. In this regard, a system for monitoring and notifying the status of the shop floor could be useful

5.1.3 Key topics from Sunlight interview process

Having a constructive discussion with the Sunlight interviewers, we have noted some useful conclusions.

1. All actors have the feeling that they are members of a serious company
2. Most of the interviewers are not thinking to seek for another job

3. Most of them are satisfied of their job and they would recommend to their friends/children to do the same work
4. There is a good teamwork between them and in case of a problem they try to solve it as a team
5. All of them are aware about safety issues and there is no doubt to use safety equipment
6. Most of the interviewers have a good relation between them and the meet each other in their free time
7. All of the actors are positive to attend any possible training and most of them are ready to perform training to their colleagues.

5.2 VOLERE REQUIREMENTS

In this section some information regarding the collected Volere requirements is provided starting from the analysis described in previous section, that allowed to identify the user requirements key findings.

In particular in the first part, Table 1 and Figure 62 show a clustering by partner and priority level plus the related percentage ratio of the Volere requirements. Following, the second part, in presents an extract of the identified requirements according to the “Volere template” methodology adopted by the SatisFactory project.

Partner	Blocker	Critical	Major	Minor	Trivial	Nice to have	TOT
ABE	0	3	0	1	0	0	4
CERTH	3	5	16	2	1	0	27
COMAU	3	5	3	3	2	1	17
FIT	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
GlassUP	0	4	0	3	0	0	7
ISMB	2	4	0	2	0	0	8
REGOLA	6	5	0	0	0	0	11
SUNLIGHT	0	5	1	1	0	0	7
TOT	14	31	21	12	3	1	82

Table 1: Volere requirements clustering

Figure 62: Volere requirements percentage & distribution

A preliminary analysis of the main referred topics among the Volere requirements collected highlights the following key findings:

- Manufacturing process monitoring & verification
- Production & maintenance documents access and guidelines
- Workload planning
- Training procedures
- Safety, ergonomics & privacy
- Communication, IoT and smart sensing
- Gestures recognition and vocal interaction
- Middleware & platform

Key	Summary	Priority	Description	Fit Criterion
SAFA-86	Online monitoring of shop floor's actors movements	Major	Actors' movements will be monitored via the thermal and the depth cameras that will be placed at the shop floor	Depth and thermal cameras will be placed inside the shop floor area, which will give necessary information to the system
SAFA-85	Data exchange from shop floor's systems with the smart sensors networks	Blocker	Smart sensors will exchange data and information with the system which will be categorized, stored and used when necessary	Many sensors will be placed at the shop floor and will be connected with the system
SAFA-84	Online access to electrical schematics and CAD drawings	Critical	Electrical schematics and other CAD drawings will be available to actors, most of the times to technicians, while they are performing various actions to the shop floor and the pilot plants	Electrical and mechanical schematics along with other drawing will be uploaded and available online for SatisFactory actors
SAFA-83	Supervisory information from the automation systems	Critical	The system will have the capability to retrieve information from all automation systems in the shop floor	Communication between SatisFactory system and automation systems will be available in order to exchange required information
SAFA-82	Online display of recorded procedures	Critical	A database in which procedures related to operation, maintenance and development actions/activities will be available in video format	Video recording infrastructure is available for logging of actions and cross-correlation with written procedures is feasible
SAFA-81	Machinery Malfunction global management system	Critical	A Malfunction management system that will prioritize the incidents and manage the resources	Technical team will work more quick and efficient
SAFA-80	Climate monitor and control system in the curing chambers	Critical	A global monitor and control system that will be able to control the temperature and the humidity in the negative plates curing chambers	Will create more suitable and stable curing conditions and the operator will be able to have a global view

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SAFA-79	Multimedia information system for Traction batteries assembly	Minor	A multimedia information system that will be available on the shop-floor to provide information for the traction batteries assembly to the workers and the trainees	Experienced workers and trainees will find any information concerning the traction battery assembly
SAFA-78	Jar Formation battery data analysis	Critical	A suitable software must be installed in the Jar Formation control units that will be able to retrieve the stored data and visualize the results	It will be easier to inspect the battery formation results
SAFA-77	Real time and continuous Monitoring of deionized water conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) coming from different reverse osmosis units	Critical	There are three different reverse osmosis units. A global supervision system will be able to monitor continuously and log the conductivity of the deionized water produced from the three units totally	Monitoring of a critical parameter will be easier and more reliable
SAFA-76	Real time and continuous Monitoring of the Cell Temperature during Jar formation	Critical	A thermal supervision system that will be installed in each Jar Formation module will supervise continuously the battery cells temperature. It will be able to provide an alarm in case that the temperature will be out of limits	The battery cells temperature should be monitored continuously which will increase the safety level and the operators will be focused to the formation process
SAFA-75	Glasses form-factor/frame	Minor	Glasses form-factor/frame has to be defined	It has to be defined for an optimal implementation in the factories.
SAFA-74	Glasses battery configuration	Critical	Battery implementation on the glasses or external via wire.	It has to be defined from the feedback of users for the optimal implementation in the factory.
SAFA-73	Data transfer between the	Critical	Data transfer between the glasses and the factory	Depending on the configuration of the data

	glasses and the factory		has to be defined.	transfer of the factory.
SAFA-72	Textual / Icons / Images information	Critical	Data set to send to the worker by the AR glasses has to be defined.	Discussion with the users and analysis of user cases will allow to define optical information to send into the eye of the worker by the glasses.
SAFA-71	Camera utilization / number of cameras	Critical	Utilization of camera on glasses depending on the user cases / number of camera to implement on glasses.	Discussion with the users and analysis of user cases will allow to take decisions on implementation of cameras and on the number of cameras needed
SAFA-70	Image position on the lens of the glasses	Minor	Definition of image position on the lens of glasses.	After tests in factory environment, from the feedback of the workers the best position for the image will be defined.
SAFA-69	Icons data platform	Minor	Definition of error / safety information like icon menu dedicated to the worker. The definition of a set of icons of immediate comprehension by the worker. The project is a worldwide project so the icons menu has to be not depending from the language of the worker. It has to be defined icons dimension too.	An icon list on errors and safety information related to factory environment is defined.

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SAFA-68	Real-time Monitoring & Verification of User activities by Sensor Data & Semantic Information	Critical	Tools, belonging to the AR platform, will allow to monitor in real time the actions carried out by the operator and test them according to the description of the operating procedures themselves, to the acquired data obtained by specific sensors placed in the workplace and to the semantic additions to assets previously monitored	annual validation, by an expert, of the results obtained from the monitoring and verification actions system implemented for the project. The system must be robust for the operating procedures provided for requirement SAFA-65 at least
SAFA-67	Uncoupling of MLD of operating procedures and their Interactive Real-time Visualization	Critical	Tools, belonging to the platform of AR, will allow to download all and only the descriptive layers of an operating procedure, in order to allow the use them according to the choices of the operator and/or to the possibility of used physical devices	Possibility of use of an OP-MLD for each of the operating procedures provided for requirement SAFA-65, by using the final AR tools developed for the project, on at least: two physical desktop configurations, two mobile devices and two wearable devices
SAFA-66	Multi-Layered Description of Operating Procedures (OP-MLD) Real-time Ready	Critical	Tool, belonging to the AR platform, will allow to translate the original operating procedures in a characteristic "multi-level description". Each level will include a specific way to describe each step of the procedure (e.g. by images, by text messages, by 3D animations, ect ...)	Availability of a MLD version of each of the operating procedures provided for requirement SAFA-65 and utilizing resources derived from the collections of the requirement SAFA-63
SAFA-65	Access to original Operating Procedures	Blocker	Tool, belonging to the AR platform, will have the ability to interpret the original operating procedures by providing a useful formalism specific to their management at runtime	Availability of three operating procedures at least, described in a formal way, by using references to 3D models and DCC data asset derived from the requirement SAFA-63

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SAFA-64	Original CAD and DCC Data Asset enrichment by semantic information	Blocker	Tool, belonging to the AR platform, will allow to add specific semantics to CAD and DCC data asset, finally saving the resulting data in a specific format	By using the collections of the requirement SAFA-63, creation of an enriched version with semantics for all assets that need it, by using the tools developed for the project
SAFA-63	Access to CAD and DCC* Data Asset	Blocker	Tool, as part of the AR platform, will have the ability to import and manage resources in standard formats, both they are related to the 3D/CAD and DCC formats	Availability of three collections of data assets at least, associated to as many operating procedures. Demonstration that the tools developed for the project properly handle such data collections
SAFA-62	Gamification	Critical	Human behavior specification with respect to ergonomic constraints standards and other HF issues	Specification document that includes references to applicable standards, union explicit or implicit acceptance.
SAFA-61	Gesture Capturing	Critical	Interface with Kinect2 for gesture capture module: semantic for gesture representation	Communication device protocol; high level data representation model and data format
SAFA-60	Personal Navigation Application	Blocker	Communication protocol with the wearable localization module.	Protocol specification document; software module interface description

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SAFA-59	Customized social communication platforms	Blocker	Detailed model for interaction (actors, data and rules)	Specification documents are accessible
SAFA-58	ACCESS TO Knowledge Base	Blocker	The Augmented Reality (AR) module will use information related to specific actions for delivering interactive training services	Data exchange protocol and metadata format is defined; software layer exist that can handle data exchange between modules
SAFA-57	The product should have a Dashboard	Minor	Dashboard for providing information on the situation at the shop-floor to enhance cooperation and interaction between all personnel (supervisors, technicians, workers).	Availability of the component, able to present at least 3 situations.
SAFA-56	Visual Analytics	Critical	The Visual Analytics Engine will provide input on views of the shop floor, production operation and workers' situations.	The Engine will be able to detect 1 event for 3 different roles.
SAFA-55	Incident Detection	Critical	The Incident Detection Engine will support the safety and comfort of workers by leveraging location information, media and gesture recognition data.	The Engine will be able to detect at least 3 potential incident events (proactive approach) and at least 3 incidents after they occur (reactive approach).

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SAFA-54	Re-adaptation of production facilities and HR workload balancing	Critical	The toolkit will provide functionalities in order to facilitate and enhance monitoring and supervision in real time, thus increasing the efficiency of the production facilities in the manufacturing shop floor.	Toolkit available and able to account for at least 3 types of normal and 3 types of not normal operation.
SAFA-53	Time validation of performed actions	Trivial	An electronic system, that will be updated dynamically and everyone could access it, will track and make a time validation of the activities within the shop floor	Most of the activities could be validated
SAFA-52	Multimedia training procedures	Blocker	Video or audio recorded procedures could be available for new operators and technicians	There are several training procedures can be performed through multimedia platform
SAFA-51	Safety verification through smart sensing	Blocker	Safety in the shop-floor can be improved by means of innovative sensing, with safety devices wearing verifications. This way all actors will use the necessary safety measures	The safety guide will be followed
SAFA-50	Standard procedures documentation	Minor	Regarding the operation of the pilot plants, there are several procedures that require standard handling with almost no changes every time. These procedures can be documented step by step in order to be easily handled by non-experienced employees.	Several procedures can be documented. There are already some documented procedures that could be improved.

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SAFA-49	Shop floor status monitoring system	Critical	The status monitoring system will provide all necessary information about the status of the shop floor to all actors	Several incidents (minor or important) could be prevented during a working day within the shop floor
SAFA-48	IT impact on aged workers	Nice to have	For young people the addition of IT technology, could be interesting, while for more aged persons, could create problems	A sustainability checklist is available
SAFA-47	Platform training	Minor	The introduction of new terminals could lead to the introduction of new training in order to let the people work with these new devices	A manual to use the platform is available
SAFA-46	Platform maintenance	Trivial	The introduction of new devices in addition to the existing ones means also the addition of activities for their maintenance	An easy-to-use environment for platform maintenance activities is available
SAFA-45	User-friendly platform	Trivial	New IT environment shall be user-friendly	The platform is easy-to-use and the required training is ≤ 1 working day
SAFA-44	Operators privacy	Major	A potential risk of limiting operators privacy is represented by the additional number of cameras and sensors that can track the activities and the time required to perform them	The records performed by the cameras are limited to real-time support functions and they are not stored
SAFA-43	Workplace IT potential risks	Minor	Introducing additional IT platform to guide the operators in their daily work activities could represent a potential risk of increasing their normal workload	Workload of operators is not increased

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SAFA-42	Workload planning support	Major	Manufacturing IT platforms should support planners to assign lighter workloads to elderly/handicapped employees	Workload planning can be performed on the basis of info collected from shop-floor
SAFA-41	Common database for shop floor data	Critical	The integration of all devices, like power tools, measuring systems (laser level), etc. could lead to the establishment of a common database where all production data could be managed	Database available, including data coming from different measuring systems used in the shop-floor
SAFA-40	Automated checklists & reporting	Critical	The application of terminals that guide the operators during the production process could lead to assisted production processes that generate automatically reports and checklists according to the operations performed	At least one automated checklist is generated by the systems at the end of a manufacturing activity
SAFA-39	Sequence of Operations real-time guidance	Critical	Workloads require that operators replace colleagues in their activities. They must have clear in mind the right Sequence of Operations, so an online guide that reminds the correct steps could avoid mistakes	At least one application containing a step-by step guide (Sequence of Operations) is available to support one manufacturing process
SAFA-38	Vocal guided procedures	Minor	Some procedures require the use of both hands. In this case the use of other senses could be a good alternative. An example could be vocal guides	At least one vocal guided procedure is available
SAFA-37	Multimedia training procedures	Blocker	IT architecture provides an innovative training environment that allows multimedia training procedures and sessions	At least 1 training procedure can be performed through multimedia platform

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SAFA-36	Smart sensing for workloads planning	Major	A good support is offered by the innovative sensing on the activities planning, coordinating the resources in order to balance the daily workloads among a team of workers, e.g. planning heavy activities in the first part of the day and light ones in the last part of the shift	Daily workload planning can be performed on the basis of ergonomics data collected from shop-floor
SAFA-35	Safety verification through smart sensing	Blocker	Safety in the shop-floor can be improved by means of innovative sensing, with safety devices wearing verifications through RFIDs or WSN applications	Safety verifications are performed via RFID/WSN sensors
SAFA-34	Smart Sensing Networks for ergonomics monitoring	Critical	Innovative sensing and actuating technologies (IoT) offer a good basis for ergonomics parameters real-time monitoring of human operators (e.g. accelerations, number of repetitive operations performed, strength required in specific operations, etc.)	Ergonomics parameter acquisitions are available for consultancy
SAFA-33	IT technology for remote functions	Critical	IT offers an enabling technology to implement remote functionalities such as production support and remote maintenance	At least 1 point-to-point remote connection is established
SAFA-32	IT platforms for data access	Blocker	IT Hardware/Software platforms provide a good support, to improve the operators access to engineering and manufacturing information and documents	At least 3 documents are available for online consultancy

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SAFA-31	DEVICE MANAGER	Critical	SATISFACTORY provides a reference implementation for the integration of devices from the physical world, abstracting their technological-specific interfaces (via DEVICE MANAGER) and exposing to the platform their capabilities and information in a common way. This will include self-discovery features of new devices, including synchronization and communication mechanisms	This software layer is available as the data entry point of the SATISFACTORY middleware
SAFA-30	SATISFACTORY Middleware	Blocker	SATISFACTORY software application layer that consists of multiple components allowing multiple entities (processes, objects, etc.) to interact with each other.	the SATISFACTORY Middleware is available to be downloaded
SAFA-29	Multi-radio technologies, enhanced power management and cooperative data acquisition	Minor	SATISFACTORY features for optimizing IoT devices performances in the working environment. Including 1) cognitive mechanisms exploiting multi-radio technologies to automatically manage available radios, 2) innovative power management features, which allows devices to adopt different operation profiles, in terms of processing and communications load and 3) cooperative data acquisition mechanisms to easily manage broad	A set of communication and energy optimization features for smart devices is available and integrated within the overall SATISFACTORY platform

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			spectrum context-related information	
SAFA-28	IoT infrastructure to enable context-aware applications	Minor	Integration within the SATISFACTORY platform of context-aware prone devices and technologies (WSANs, wearables, UWB nodes).	The DEVICE MANAGER includes PROXIEs or DRIVERs to interoperate with context-aware devices

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SAFA-27	Context aware incident detection	Critical	<p>The development of a context manager in a faster and more contextualized environment, acts as an enabler to enhance workers safety. Three components are required to enable the input information flow to the context manager. The first is the localization manager, that allows to increase knowledge of workers position at the shop floor level. The second is the multiple-media manager, a components that enriches localization data with visual information. The third component, the gesture and content recognition manager, is in charge of detecting potential risks in the production facility. All the above components will be developed with privacy preservation and safety enhancement through virtual fencing and incident detection mechanisms.</p>	The described components are directly correlated to safety enhancing procedures and will forward important information demanded by the event manager, among other components.
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SAFA-26	<p>Novel toolkit to increase production at shop-floor level</p>	<p>Critical</p>	<p>A novel toolkit will be created, deploying semantically enhanced functionalities at the shop floor level, providing real-time information about the production process and its evolution, allowing real time monitoring. This goal will be achieved combining information coming from the shop floor from a smart sensor network and from optical and thermal sensors. The expected output includes the ability of calibrate facility operating parameters and trigger specific events related to both maintenance or safety procedure, based on a model of the specific production facility.</p>	<p>The toolkit acts as a driver for propagating and recognizes critical situations.</p>
SAFA-25	<p>Creation of social interaction platform</p>	<p>Critical</p>	<p>The creation of a social interaction platform is an enabler to improve and enhance interactions between employees. The platform foresees the combination of contextual information, compliant with the SatisFactory knowledge scheme, with a digital Andon system, fully integrated with HMIs and mobile devices, in order to enhance social collaboration. Finally, the platform will be interfaced with the event manager, allowing this component to make contextual information available to other</p>	<p>Platform is an enabler for enhancing workers satisfaction.</p>

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			components, achieving a context-aware infrastructure.	
SAFA-24	Common Information Data Exchange Model - CIDEM	Blocker	The CIDEM is the modelling framework which semantically enriches representation of application-domain-specific resources and a low level adaptation interfaces. It exposes resources (data, event, services), interfaces and applications in a common way	The CIDEM reference framework is available (identified among existing data models in SOTA or newly designed for the SATISFACTORY project)
SAFA-23	The product shall incorporate tablet PCs	Major	An interviewee in CERTH requested that selected and filtered information from the existing automation systems will be available at the mobile device (eg tablet) of the involved workers.	Automation systems can be monitored and partially operated/controlled from a tablet PC
SAFA-22	The product shall provide generic situation information on public displays	Minor	A screen will be available to inform the workers about the activities which are performed at the shop floor and the respective time-schedule combined with prioritization and	The system provides generic situation of procedures performed at the shop floor to displays that can be seen the shop floor workers

			criticality information	
SAFA-21	The product shall boost collaboration	Major	Team work and collaboration is considered highly valuable in the work. The product shall encourage and boost this. A respective component shall be available to enable information exchange and online status monitoring for each workers	A survey among 10 workers reveals that at least 3 consider the product to boost collaboration
SAFA-19	Personal protection equipment usage reminder	Critical	All actions within the shop floor must be perform with the necessary safety measures. Thus, the system will remind the actor which measures must be used according to the performed action	All actors involved at the shop floor would be reminded to use the necessary personal safety measures such as gloves, helmet, glasses working aprons etc. when working at the shop floor
SAFA-18	Support maintenance actions	Major	Maintenance procedures will be recorded in order to be available to actors when necessary. They could be access via a tablet or a pc and actors will be guided how to perform the specific action	All maintenance actions and procedures could be recorded
SAFA-17	The product shall integrate with existing collaboration platforms	Major	Collaboration platforms like internal Wikis are used at CERTH for documentation	Documents from the product shall be compatible with the existing collaboration platforms and vice versa
SAFA-16	The product shall not interfere with the work flexibility	Major	The work at CERTH is very flexible. Workers are assigned goals which need to be fulfilled. It is up to them when and how to fulfill them. The product	After the introduction of the product, CERTH workers are able to fulfill their goals when and how they want.

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			shall not change this flexibility.	
SAFA-15	The product shall be applicable for different workday schedules	Major	The workday schedule of process operators is completely different when there is an experiment that day. For example, units are not shut down.	The system is applicable to days when there is an experiment and to normal operation days.
SAFA-14	The product shall reduce the number of mistakes by operators	Major	The job of operators is always the same. This leads to an increased number of mistakes	The number of mistakes by operators is reduced after the product is installed.
SAFA-13	The product shall be available 24h a day	Major	CERTH is operating 24h each day, so the product shall be available all that time	The product is available 24 hours a day.
SAFA-12	The visually augmented mapping of the process onto unit's components shall be easy to understand	Major	The visualized mapping of the process onto unit's components shall be easy to understand to Process Operators	90% of the test probands are able to map any of 10 randomly selected process steps onto the unit within 15 seconds with help of the product.

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SAFA-11	The system shall visually augment the mapping of the process that is implemented in the unit onto the unit's components	Major	The system shall visualize the mapping of the process that is implemented in the unit onto the unit's components, e.g. it shall augment what pipes are currently in use and what kind of gas flows in each of them.	For every step of the process there is a one-to-one correspondence in the unit's components that is shown in the interface.
SAFA-10	The product shall increase healthiness of work	Major	The work with petrochemicals, gases or fuels is considered unhealthy.	A survey among 10 workers reveals that at least 3 of them consider the product as improving the health conditions of the workplace.
SAFA-9	The product shall reduce personal misunderstandings	Major	Due to the huge number of people, misunderstandings often occur.	A survey among 10 workers reveals that at least 3 the product helps avoiding misunderstandings among workers.
SAFA-8	The number of false alarms shall be reduced	Major	Currently, there are daily false alarms because the alarm settings for gases are very sensitive.	After the introduction of the product the number of false alarms per month is reduced by 30% compared to the number of false alarms before the introduction of the product.
SAFA-7	The product shall not emit noxious gases or substances that damage people's health	Major	Especially at SUNLIGHT and CERTH that work with noxious and explosive substances the product/solution/system shall not allow for emission of these substances that are dangerous for health.	The product shall be certified by qualified maintenance engineers.

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SAFA-6	The product shall be used by people with no training, and possibly no understanding of English	Major	The product shall be easy to use, so that no training, and no understanding of English is required for it use.	A sampling of representative workers shall, without reading user manual or being trained with the product, start using the product within four minutes of their first encounter with it and during their use do not require help from outside related to the product's interface.
SAFA-5	The product shall appear trustworthy	Major	The product shall appear trustworthy to the users, and thus support the perception of the working environment as safe and trustworthy.	After their first encounter with the product, 70% of representative potential users shall agree they feel they can trust the product.
SAFA-4	The product shall be attractive to young job-seekers	Major	The product/system/solution shall appeal to young unemployed people.	A sampling of representative young job-seekers are, after five minutes of using the product, are willing to use it further and recommend the product to their friends.
SAFA-3	Mechanical operator needs to have means for lifting and moving heavy mechanical components available, in order to relocate them from workbench to pallet	-	In COMAU Robotics shop-floor operators say that the fixtures available to move heavy mechanical components from workbench to pallet are not safe and efficient enough, because currently they are using belts and chain which are generic tools that do not fix the parts properly (parts could move/rotate/fall down if not properly fixed).	

Table 2: Jira - Volere requirements

CONCLUSIONS

The present document is the first deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020), reporting the results of the activities carried out by WP1, that will manage and undertake the work in carrying out the iterative engineering of requirements, which special focuses on the engineering process of initial requirements and reengineering after the end of each iteration cycle.

Moreover this Workpackage maintains a continuous discovery and analysis of user centric requirements, needs and prospects, to be used in the design, development, implementation and validation of the SatisFactory platform and services.

The main achievements reported in this document are the description of the requirements to be addressed in the prototype applications for the three end-users test-beds: discrete manufacturing in automotive, discrete manufacturing for batteries and continuous process in chemical applications. Specifically, the goal of this document is to define the a list of initial requirements exploiting the "Volere" approach, that will be continuously updated and refined through an iterative process that will lead to the production of a total of three releases of this deliverable, respectively in Project Months M4, M14 and M26.

In particular, it is worth to highlight that the collection of requirements, performed through more than forty (40) face-to-face interviews of end-user employees, followed by brainstorming sessions among technology partners, provided more than eighty-three (83) initial requirements.

These topics will be the main areas of improvement that the SatisFactory project will consider during the future development phases performed in the technical Workpackages and validated through an iterative process.

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ANNEX 1 – INTERVIEW NOTES AND TEMPLATE

Notes & guidelines for conducting the interviews

General Tips:

- Project presentation
- Data will remain confidential
- Only aggregated data will be shown at the end
- Create a friendly atmosphere: make small talk
- Distance yourself from the enterprise and make clear that the answers will be confidential, best: Hire someone external to do this. Psychology/Sociology students will be fine
- This interview should feel like two friends in a coffee bar
- Use these questions for you, to steer the conversation
- Change them as you see fit for the situation
- Set a hierarchy of questions in your mind and be ready to leave out non-essential questions in favour of important ones
- Remember that we are trying to improve happiness and satisfaction
- Questions allowed: Who, What, Why, What for, How, When

Section 1 –Company general information

1. What is the company's core business? [Industry sector]
2. Total revenues in 2014? [MEuro]
3. Number of Employees at the end of 2014? [Number]

Section 2 – Stakeholder general information

1. Contact information? [person name, age, phone, email]
2. Which is your education degree? [Vocational, BS, MS]
3. What is your actual role in the company? [Job title]
4. Years of experience in the actual role? [Number]
5. Which are your main areas of expertise? [3-5 areas]
6. How did you come to do this job? [Social, Newspapers, Networking]
7. What is best & worst about working in this field/job?
8. Would you recommend your son/daughter/friend to do the same job? [Y/N, Why?]

Section 3 – Activities/Work description

1. Which are your/your workers' "typical working day" activities?
2. Can you describe your workplace?
3. What tools do you use for your work? [Nr, type]
4. How do you do your work, what is involved in the process?
5. Do you use any specific safety device? [Safety shoes, gloves, glasses, helmet]
6. How is your working time organized? How much flexibility do you have with it?
 - a. How do you feel about that?
7. What procedures are there to validate timing and quality of the work performed?

8. What extraordinary activities are there in your working day?
 - a. What happens rarely, but is problematic or disturbing to you?
9. Do you perform your daily activities individually or in collaboration with others?
 - a. How do you collaborate with them?

Section 4 – Employees turnover

1. How many years do you think people stay in the company on average?
2. How much time does it take to fill a job opening?
3. Most common reasons for people going away?
4. Most common reason for the length it takes to fill an opening?
5. What has been tried to increase satisfaction/lower turnover? What were the results?

Section 5 – Training received

1. What training did you get for this work?
 - a. How long did the training period last?
 - b. How many years ago it was performed?
 - c. How would you train someone to do your job? Or, how would you have wished to be trained?

Section 6 – Procedures and guidelines applied (plus IT support)

1. In your working activities what specific procedures do you follow? What is good and what is bad about them?
2. What documents are there to guide you in these procedures, or what documents are needed as part of these procedures?
3. What electronic devices do you use in these procedures? [Computers, Tablet, HMI, ...]
4. How are the procedures or work orders told to you?

Section 7 – Working scenario improvement

1. What bothers you most about your work? How would you improve it?
2. Do you think that the actual procedures and guidelines could be improved?
3. Do you think that the actual IT support to access the existing procedures should be improved? (e.g. introducing terminals, touchscreens, mobile devices....)
4. Do you feel the need of some additional training?
5. In the complex, which is your degree of satisfaction of the actual workplace?

Section 8 – Other suggestions

1. Do you have any other suggestion?

ANNEX 2 – REQUIREMENTS TEMPLATE (VOLERE)

Requirement No.:	Requirement Type:	Use Cases:
Description:		
Rationale:		
Source:		
Fit Criterion:		
Customer Satisfaction Rating:	Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:	
Dependencies:	Conflicts:	
History:	Supporting Materials:	

ANNEX 3 – LEGISLATION REVIEW

EUROPEAN LEGISLATION

The EU has established the legal framework which is categorised below.

PERSONAL DATA

- **Protection of personal data**

The protection of personal data is ensured by Directive 95/46/EC on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. The Directive applies to the processing of individuals' personal data by other individuals, businesses, public authorities, etc. This concerns the processing of data wholly or partly by automatic means and the processing of data that form part of a filing system.

The aim of the Directive is to protect the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals, in particular their right to privacy with respect to the processing of personal data. Under the Directive, data must be collected fairly and lawfully, which means collection for specified and legitimate purposes. Furthermore, the data must be accurate and not excessive in relation to the purposes for which it was collected. The Directive forbids the keeping of the data for longer than necessary. The organisation collecting the data is under the obligation to ensure the confidentiality and security of their processing. The processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs and trade-union membership is forbidden, as is the processing of data concerning health or sex life. This does however not apply when the person involved has given his or her explicit consent or when the processing is necessary for employment law purposes, in which case adequate safeguards will need to be provided. The person on whom data is being collected must be informed of the identity of the organisation collecting that data and of its reason for doing so. The Directive also gives individuals the right to access data held on them except in certain cases such as police and HM Revenue & Customs records. In addition, the Directive provides for the right to have the data corrected and the right to object to certain types of data being processed in some instances.

The organisation collecting and processing the data is under the obligation to notify an independent supervisory body before carrying out wholly or partly automatic data processing operations. Those in business in the EU therefore have to register and ensure that they have procedures in place to give individuals copies of the data held on them. Those who suffer damage because of unlawful processing have a right to sue for damages. Individuals are also given the right to object to their data being held for direct marketing purposes.

INFORMATION AND CONSULTATION OF EMPLOYEES

- **Informing and consulting employees**

Directive 2002/14/EC establishes a general framework for informing and consulting employees in the European Community. The purpose of this Directive is to establish a general framework setting out minimum requirements for employees' rights and for consultation of employees in undertakings or establishments across the EU. The scope of the Directive is restricted to undertakings with minimum 50 employees or establishments employing at least 20 employees. The Directive outlines broad guidelines and practical arrangements that are to be defined and implemented in accordance with national law and industrial relations practices in the individual Member States.

Under the Directive, employers have to disclose any information regarding the recent and probable development of the organisation's activities and economic situation. Employees also have to be kept informed of the situation of employment within the undertaking or establishment and of any envisaged measures, in particular when there is a threat to employment. Finally, decisions likely to lead to substantial changes in the work organisation or contractual relations have to be made known to employees. The information has to be given at such a time, in such a fashion and with such content as is appropriate to enable employees' representatives to carry out an adequate study and, where necessary, prepare for consultation. Consultation has to be organised at the appropriate time at the relevant level of management and representation, and in such a way that enables employees' representatives to meet the employer and obtain a response. The Directive does not cover confidential information.

ANTI-DISCRIMINATION

- **Workplace discrimination**

Directive 2000/78/EC establishes a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation, which forbids discrimination based on religion, belief, disability, age and sexual orientation.

- **Racial and ethnic discrimination**

The general principle of anti-discrimination is safeguarded at the EU level by Directive 2000/43/EC implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin. The Directive covers areas such as education, social protection (social security and healthcare), social advantages and access to and supply of goods and services and goes beyond access to employment and self-employment (covered by Directive 2000/78/EC outlined above).

- **Equal treatment of men and women in the workplace**

Equality between men and women in the workplace is guaranteed by three pieces of EU legislation.

- **The Equal Pay Directive**

Directive 75/117/EC on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to the application of the principle of equal pay for men and women.

- **The Equal Treatment Directive**

Directive 76/207/EC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and working conditions. (Directive 2002/73/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 September 2002 amending Council Directive

76/207/EEC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions, Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation).

- **The Equal Social Security Directive**

Directive 86/378/EEC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women in occupational social security schemes.

GREEK LEGISLATION

The Greek legislation is in accordance to the EU legislation. In Greece, the law N. 2472/1997 (and amendments N. 3471/2006, N. 3783/2009, N. 3917/2011, N. 4070/2012 and N. 4139/2013), define the framework for the protection of personal data. The individuals, in relation to data collection, have the rights to: information, access, objection, interim judicial protection. Personal data is any piece information referring to the "data subject", the individual. "Data Subject" is the natural person to whom the data refer and whose identity is known or can be ascertained, that can be determined directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identification number or to one or more factors specific to his or her physiological, mental, economic, cultural, political or social substance.

According to article 7A of N. 2472/1997 the monitoring party is exempted from the notification requirement in some cases, one of which is: "When the processing is done by unions, companies, firms, associations and political parties and relates to data of their members or their companies if they have given their consent and data is not transmitted or communicated to third parties". It is noted that the monitoring is part of SatisFactory project and that the companies providing the pilot plants are partners in the project. It would be preferable that the employees participating in the pilot trial give their consent.

The Hellenic Data Protection Authority issues Directives on related matters. The most relative to our project are:

Directive 115/2001 was issued for the interpretation of law N. 2472/1997 and N. 2774/99. This Directive explicitly notes examples of recruitment procedures, in the attempt to interpret the legislation. It is stated that the personal data of the employees must be collected and processed for precisely defined purposes. Under the N. 2472/1997 law, the employer is obliged to inform the workers, and this suggests that the purposes of the processing should be known in advance to employees and understood by them.

Personal data collected in connection with technical or organizational measures to ensure the correct and safe system operation cannot be used to control the behaviour of employees, unless it is associated with the operation of these systems.

Modern methods of personnel selection include examinations, tests or procedures for the assessment of qualifications, skills and abilities of the candidate. These examinations and analysis may reveal or make reference to aspects of personality, related beliefs, traditions and spiritual or mental health / condition of a person. Due to the nature of the data, their collection is legally permissible only with the written consent of the candidate, and after informing him/her about the method, criteria, objectives and (potential) recipients of the analysis and results. The applicant

should be informed of the results and the data should be erased or destroyed as soon they fulfil the purpose of collection, unless the applicant specifically requests the preservation of the data.

Regarding personal data concerning the health of the worker or candidate must be collected directly and only by the workers or candidates and only as long as it is absolutely necessary for the evaluation of the suitability of the employee or candidate for a specific position or job. The collection of personal data using control methods and monitoring of workers must be limited to the data that are directly related to the employment and should not be extended to the personal behaviour, characteristics or personal internal and external contacts of the workers. Continuous control should only occur if it is justified by the nature and conditions of work and if it is necessary to protect the health and safety of workers and the safety of workplaces.

Directive 1/2005 on the secure destruction of personal data, after the time needed after the period required to carry out the purpose that required processing of the data. It is noted that this Directive shall not apply in the case that the data is rendered anonymous by the controller after the end of the treatment period.

Moreover, the Greek Constitution (1975/1986/2001) recognises the principle of privacy, which in fact is a combination of the protection of human dignity, liberty, the confidentiality of communications and the imposition of restrictions on state and private economic activity. This principle implies the right of everyone to protect his/her dignity, his/her freedom, the space in which he/she is moving and his/her personal activities, from any carrier and any process.

ITALIAN LEGISLATION

The Italian legislation is in general accordance with EU legislation. The main reference code is Data Protection Code - Legislative Decree no. 196/2003.

Introduction

Italy's consolidated data protection code came into force on 1 January 2004. The Code brings together all the various laws, codes and regulations relating to data protection since 1996. In particular, it supersedes the Data Protection Act 1996 (no. 675/1996), which had come into effect in May 1997.

There are three key guiding principles behind the code, which are outlined in section 2:

1. Simplification
2. Harmonization
3. Effectiveness

The code is divided into three parts. The first part sets out the general data protection principles that apply to all organizations. Part two of the code provides additional measures that will need to be undertaken by organizations in certain areas, for example, healthcare, telecommunications, banking and finance, or human resources. Part three relates to sanctions and remedies. It is expected that the second part of the code will be developed further through the introduction of sectorial codes of practice.

Scope of the Italian data protection code - The code applies to all processing within the State and its territories. It will also affect outside organizations that make use of equipment located within Italy, which could include e.g. PCs and other computer-based systems (see Section 5 of the Code). If an organization outside the EU is processing data on Italian territory, it must appoint a representative in Italy for the application of Italian rules (this will be necessary for notifying with the "Garante", if notification is due, and providing data subjects with information notices).

Main Features of the Data Protection Code

Notification - One of the key targets for simplification was the notification process, which was made more straightforward compared to the 1996 Act in line with the EU Data Protection Directive - which allows the notification process to be simplified in cases where data processing does not adversely affect the rights and freedoms of data subjects (see Article 18(2) of the directive). Under the Italian code, organizations are only required to notify the "Garante" when processing higher-risk categories of data. These include, in particular, genetic and biometric data, data processed for the purpose of analyzing or profiling individuals, and credit-related information (see Section 37 of the code for additional details). This approach is also aimed at making the process more transparent and understandable for individuals.

Data minimization - Section 3 of the code introduces the element of data minimization into Italian data protection. The code encourages organizations to make use of non-personal data whenever possible.

Data subjects' rights/Decision taking - The code aims to strengthen individuals' data protection rights, allowing them to exercise their rights and instigate proceedings more easily. In an effort to simplify the complaints process, the "Garante" has published a complaints form on its website. The "Garante" can also order businesses to abide by compliance requirements set out in its decisions. When responding to investigations, businesses now have 15 days to comply, compared to the previous 5-day timeframe. The turnaround for dealing with complaints has been raised to 60 days (previously it was 30 days); this period was found to be suitable in order for the "Garante" to work effectively and the parties to prepare their pleadings appropriately.

International Data Transfers - The data protection Code has incorporated and, to some extent, updated the previous rules on data transfers (data transfers are addressed in Sections 42-45 of the Code). Whereas previously businesses had to notify the "Garante" of their intention to transfer data outside the EU, under the new system companies will only have to provide notification in cases in which the transfer of data could prejudice data subjects' rights (see the Notification section). Additionally, the new system does not require organizations to resubmit notifications each year. The rules for legitimizing transfers to non-EU countries can be found in Section 43 of the Code and include consent, meeting contractual obligations, public interest requirements, safeguarding life/health, investigations by defense counsel, use of publicly available data, processing for statistical/historical purposes. Additional provisions for legitimizing transfers are laid out in Section 44 of the Code and include transfers to countries deemed adequate by the European Commission,

the adoption of contractual safeguards, and the use of binding corporate rules. Data subjects are entitled to lodge claims in Italy for non-compliance with the said contractual/corporate safeguards.

Main Features in Respect of Specific Processing Operations

Human Resources Data - The code has fully implemented Article 8 (b) of the EU directive which applies to the processing of data. Organizations processing sensitive data that wish to find an alternative to the somewhat unreliable issues of employee consent, can look at the exemptions laid out in Section 26 of the code. For example, Section 26 (4d) allows the processing of sensitive data without consent if necessary to meet obligations under employment law.

Health data - Processing is allowed with the data subject's consent (which must be provided in writing) and the Garante's authorisation if the data controller is a private body. As for public bodies, processing is allowed if it is provided for in laws/regulations; however, the latter must set out the specific processing operations and purposes in detail, otherwise the relevant public bodies must specify them via ad-hoc regulatory instruments. The data subject's consent is not required, in principle, whilst the Garante's authorisation is necessary except for the processing by health care professionals that is indispensable with a view to the data subject's health and/or bodily integrity. The Garante's authorisation has been granted in the form of an instrument applying to several entities and/or processing operations, i.e. as a "General Authorization for the Processing of Sensitive Data" by various categories of data controller (see Legislation section). It should be recalled that specific provisions are laid down in the DP Code to regulate the processing of medical data in the health care sector (Sections 75-94). In particular, health care professionals and public health care bodies may process medical data (the Code refers to "data suitable for disclosing health") with the data subject's consent and without the Garante's authorization if the processing concerns data and operations that are indispensable with a view to the data subject's health and/or bodily integrity; conversely, they may process medical data without the data subject's consent but with the Garante's authorization if the processing is indispensable to safeguard public health.

Electronic Communications Data - The Code has implemented the provisions contained in the E-Communications privacy directive 2002/58/EC as well as in the data retention directive (2006/24/EC) (see Title 10, Part 2 of the Code). One of the main principles is on electronic marketing which requires organizations to obtain prior consent before sending electronic marketing to consumers (see Section 130). This applies to all forms of e-marketing, including e-mail, fax, SMS/MMS etc.. Specific provisions were added to regulate telemarketing. There is also a ban on sending e-marketing from anonymous addresses - this is a breach of the data protection code as the data controller has withheld its identity. As for data retention, communications service providers (CSPs) are permitted to retain traffic data for only a six-month period in order to deal with disputes over billing and subscriber services (section 123(2)). CSPs are also required to retain traffic data for longer in connection with law enforcement purposes; the retention periods are currently set at twenty-four months (telephone traffic data) and twelve months (electronic communications traffic data), irrespective of the given offence at issue (in pursuance of directive 2006/24/EC) (see section 132). Following ratification of Council of Europe's Cybercrime Convention (via Act no. 48/2008,

which amended Section 132 of the DP Code), police authorities were enabled, under specific circumstances, to order IT and/or Internet service providers and operators to retain and protect Internet traffic data - except for contents data- for no longer than ninety days, in order to carry out pre-trial investigations or else with a view to the detection and suppression of specific offences. The order issued by police authorities must be notified to and validated by the competent public prosecutor.

Main Features as to Compliance and Enforcement

Complaints - Data subjects can settle disputes either through the courts or by lodging a complaint with the Garante in case they have been prevented from exercising access, erasure, rectification, updating rights (as per Section 7 of the code). Organisations have 30 15 days to respond and can appeal to the Garante for more time. The Garante will then have 60 days to consider the request (see above "Data Subjects' Rights/Decision Taking").

Inspections - The Garante's inspection powers are laid out in Section 158 of the code. When investigating organizations, the Garante can request information and documents, although these requests are not legally binding. However, if there is no cooperation, and the organizations refuses access to its systems, the Garante can apply for a judicial order to carry out an investigation.

When carrying out formal inspections, the Garante can demand copies of manual records and databases, which may be passed onto the judicial authorities. A report of the outcome is then published.

CONCLUSION

Consequently, for the implementation of T1.1 Satisfactory, contacting workers and stakeholders through questionnaires or interviews does not oppose to current legislation, as long as we keep them informed on the type of data collected, processed and stored, on the scope of the data collection and as long as we have their consent (for the case of collection of personal data).

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ANNEX 4 – WORKPLACES ERGONOMICS

GENERAL ASPECTS

In order to achieve a full transformation of factories into attractive workplaces, designing factories as places that provide pleasant working experience, it is necessary to take into consideration also the aspects related to the interaction between workers and machines (safety and ergonomics).

Ergonomics, according to International Ergonomics Association, is “the scientific discipline concerned with the understanding of interactions among humans and other elements of a system, and the profession that applies theory, principles, data and methods to design in order to optimize human well-being and overall system performance”.

We usually refer to ergonomics meaning all actions taken to guarantee a satisfactory working condition under general constraints of health and safety regulations.

The European Community directives on safety at work and their national implementations have given a new and deeper impulse to the study of working places more and more satisfying for the workers. We can say that the directives have given a very strong impulse to develop harmonized standards and draft standards on the issues of ergonomics. The comfort in work environment is now gaining increasing importance under the pressure of the market, and there is therefore a higher attention of the European legislation for this issue.

However, it must be noted that the quantity and breadth of these standards are not even remotely comparable with standards developed in other fields, such as that of the machine safety. While the ergonomics science is now widespread (at least in all industrially developed countries), with many years of practice, we have to remark that from the point of view of practical solutions, consolidated applications are still missing.

The social policy of European Community states, but also from other continents (North America), is now increasingly appreciating the benefits deriving from a new approach towards working conditions as an important enabling factor to enhance overall profitability. Very often, however, a traditional approach tends to consider ergonomics as an additional cost for machinery and equipment, neglecting thus the crucial aspect that comfortable workplaces bring many and important benefits to the factory productivity (from economic as well as from social point of view). Anyway, at least in the first implementation phases, additional expenses and investments are undeniably needed to ensure a safe and comfortable working environment.

Companies operating in a mass production paradigm must know the level of performance of the worker and strive to improve working efficiency: this is especially true where the employee are delegated tasks more and more complex, due to the greater flexibility of man if compared with machines (even automatic). If we consider a typical automotive scenario, in usual practice assembly lines composed by a large number of manual stations show significant advantages in terms of production flexibility improvements, but there is a typical drawback in terms of production efficiency of the system when the cycle time of manual stations becomes very low. This may be very well highlighted through a virtual discrete event simulation. The reason of production worsening lies in the fact that the workers employed in a specific manual workstations cannot keep the cycle

theoretically assigned to them during the shift, if this cycle has not been previously calculated and thoroughly determined with the scientific and technical tools developed by ergonomic science. This is a first proof that ergonomics compliance costs may be highly compensated for by related productive benefits.

We can say that the calculation of the cycle time for manual or semiautomatic workstations are not possible without a careful ergonomic analysis, which will have to verify the correctness of the cycle time calculated by the formal tools of Work Analysis.

Fig. 1 - Health risk associated with postures

Figure 2: A model of the health risks associated with postures and movements

Fig. 2 - Dimensions for human-machinery interaction

The combined use of Work Analysis and Ergonomic Load can provide very useful information to verify the theoretical productivity of an assembly plant and thus its overall actual performance. The calculation of cycle time (starting from the analysis of micro-movements related to the task to be performed), verified through ergonomic and safety analysis, in conjunction with the discrete event simulation of production process, will enable a reasonable confidence of overall system performance. Furthermore, with the study of Life Cycle Cost, it will be possible to compare different options for systems layout, for manual/automatic stations as well as mixed solutions.

The careful ergonomic study of the working stations, combined with the system simulation, may suggest improvements related to different configurations and balance of the same stations. The analysis may give indications on the possibility to add or remove operations at a given station to increase or reduce the cycle time (therefore affecting the ergonomic load), keeping under control the ultimate goal of the overall productivity of the line, through the measurement of its global performance.

In general, ergonomic science was conceived starting from the concept that the human worker comes first, and then the environment and working equipment is built around him.

RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Complete this worksheet following the step-by-step procedure below. Keep a copy in the employee's personnel folder for future reference.

A. Arm & Wrist Analysis

Step 1: Locate Upper Arm Position

Step 2: Locate Lower Arm Position

Step 3: Locate Wrist Position

Step 4: Wrist Twist

Step 5: Look-up Posture Score in Table A

Step 6: Add Muscle Use Score

Step 7: Add Force/load Score

Step 8: Find Row in Table C

SCORES

Table A

Table B

Table C

B. Neck, Trunk & Leg Analysis

Step 9: Locate Neck Position

Step 10: Locate Trunk Position

Step 11: Legs

Step 12: Look-up Posture Score in Table B

Step 13: Add Muscle Use Score

Step 14: Add Force/load Score

Step 15: Find Column in Table C

Subject: _____ Date: ____/____/____
 Company: _____ Department: _____ Scorer: ____/____/____

FINAL SCORE: 1 or 2 = Acceptable; 3 or 4 investigate further; 5 or 6 investigate further and change soon; 7 investigate and change immediately
 Source: McLamney, L. & Corlett, E.N. (1993) RULA: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders, *Applied Ergonomics*, 24(2) 91-99.
 © Professor Alan Hedge, Cornell University, Feb. 2001

Fig. 3 - Example of employees ergonomics assessment table

This concept, expressed as a formal need and objective, should gradually evolve from the stage of theoretical analysis to a wide practical implementation, considering all factors possibly influencing the technical solutions to be devised.

Table 1: Recommended mass constant (M_c) taking into consideration the intended user populations

Field of application	M_c : kg	Percentage of population group				
		F&M	F	M		
Domestic use	5	Data not available			Children and the elderly	Total population
	10	99	99	99		
Professional use	15	95	90	99	General working population, including the young and old	General working population
	25	85	70	90		
	30	Data not available			Specialized working population	Specialized working population under special circumstances
	35					
40						

F: Female M: Male
 NOTE: Special circumstances
 While every effort should be made to avoid manual handling activities or reduce the risks to the lowest possible levels, there may be exceptional circumstances where the recommended mass constant may exceed 25 kg (e.g. where technological developments or interventions are not sufficiently advanced). In these exceptional circumstances, special consideration must be given to the education and training of the individual (e.g. specialized knowledge concerning risk identification and risk reduction), the working conditions which prevail and the capabilities of the individual.

Fig. 4 - Examples of measurement tables for work loads

A wide implementation of ergonomics in industrial environment requires nevertheless a great work in systematically designing specific feasible solutions for any technical scenario, thus allowing to embed ergonomic compliance during design phase without additional effort.

Simulation tools play a big role in implementing ergonomics.

Fig. 5 - Example of s/w simulation of working station

The main problem of simulation is that very often ergonomic standards (e.g. for effort limits and anthropometric measurements) are different between Europe and other states like US. This problem is present at any level in legislation.

European legislation sometimes refers, in the regulations for the practical implementation of laws, to rules issued by US authorities, even when similar issues have been dealt with by European harmonized standards. On the other hand individual states, but also local governments, normally issue their own regulations, which finally become a legal constraint to be respected by manufacturers and end-users of machinery.

A strong need for harmonization is required, to avoid having different laws and regulation in different states in the same context, with the consequent additional effort for machinery producer. The European Union is undeniably making a big effort in issuing complete and extensive ergonomic norms, even if for some issues there is still the need to refer to US standards, while for others no standards are available as yet.

RELEVANT STANDARDS IN ERGONOMICS AND FIELDS OF APPLICATION

The concept of ergonomics is closely connected with safety: we can hardly speak of ergonomics if we do not address the issues of security and vice versa. The two aspects of safety and ergonomics are complementary: a machine must be safe, but must also be manageable by workers in all operating conditions, and therefore it must also be ergonomic.

It is not conceivable to have a safe machine, but unmanageable by the worker in production or maintenance phase: sooner or later, the workers would be trying to bypass safety equipment to fully operate the machinery.

We can therefore say that a theoretically safe machine, which is not also ergonomic, will not be really safe, as it will inherently lead to non-safe behaviour by the human operator. The contrary is not true, since ergonomics takes formally into account all aspects of human-machine interaction, and thus the safety requirements as well. Thus, an ergonomic machine will be also safe by definition.

Table 1

	Static posture	Movement	
		low frequency (< 2/minute)	high frequency (≥ 2 /minute)
I*	acceptable	ACCEPTABLE	acceptable
II	conditionally acceptable (step 2A)	acceptable	not acceptable
III	not acceptable	conditionally acceptable (step 2C)	not acceptable
IV	conditionally acceptable (step 2B)	conditionally acceptable (step 2C)	not acceptable

Figure 3: Trunk bending forward/backward • It is recommended to strive for working postures with an upright trunk.

Fig. 6 - Examples of table for workers right posture

If we consider the application area of manufacturing systems, we have many applicable standards referring in general to safety/ergonomics.

Fig. 7 - Example of weight lifting posture

Focusing mainly on European/USA areas, we can list the following norms as highly relevant to the design of manufacturing plants and machinery:

- EN 547-1 "Safety of machinery. Human body measurements. Principles for determining the dimensions required for openings for whole body access into machinery"
- EN 547-2 "Safety of machinery. Human body measurements. Principles for determining the dimensions required for access openings"
- EN 547-3 "Safety of machinery. Human body measurements. Anthropometric data"
- EN 1005-1 "Safety of machinery. Human physical performance. Part 1: Terms and definitions"
- EN 1005-2 "Safety of machinery. Human physical performance. Part 2: Manual handling of machinery and component parts of machinery"

- EN 1005-3 "Safety of machinery. Human physical performance. Part 3: Recommended force limits for machinery operations"
- EN 1005-4 "Safety of machinery. Human physical performance. Part 4: Evaluation of working postures and movements in relation to machinery"
- EN 1005-5 "Safety of machinery. Human physical performance. Part 5: Risk assessment for repetitive handling at high frequency"
- ISO 11228-1 "Ergonomics. Manual handling. Part 1: Lifting and carrying"
- ISO 11228-2 "Ergonomics. Manual handling. Part 2: Pushing and pulling"
- ISO 11228-3 "Ergonomics. Manual handling. Part 3: Handling of low loads at high frequency"
- ISO EN 14738 "Safety of machinery. Anthropometric requirements for the design of workstations at machinery"
- EN 614-1 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomic design principles. Terminology and general principles"
- EN 614-2 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomic design principles. Part 2: Interactions between the design of machinery and work tasks"
- ISO EN 894-1 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomics requirements for the design of displays and control actuators. General principles for human interactions with displays and control actuators"
- ISO EN 894-2 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomics requirements for the design of displays and control actuators. Displays"
- ISO EN 894-3 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomics requirements for the design of displays and control actuators. Control actuators"
- ISO EN 894-4 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomics requirements for the design of displays and control actuators. Location and arrangement of displays and control actuators"
- ISO EN 7250-1 "Basic human body measurements for technological design. Part 1: Body measurement definitions and landmarks"
- ISO EN 7250-2 "Basic human body measurements for technological design. Part 2: Statistical summaries of body measurements from national populations"

Fig. 8 - Examples of field of application of standards

Other relevant guidelines for enhancing ergonomics in factories may be found under OHSAS 18001 (“OHSAS: Occupation Health and Safety Assessment Series”), a specification for safety management systems inside organizations.

Fig. 9 - OHS Management System

Another important source of information is represented by US NIOSH (National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health) standards.

Fig. 10 - example of job stress model bu NIOSH

Each norm deals with specific subjects referred to the interaction between the human worker and the machinery, establishing the average values to be taken as a reference in designing machines.

ANNEX 5 – INFORMED CONSENT FOR INTERVIEWS

[PILOT SITE]

(COMAU, SUNLIGHT, CERTH)

Project Title: *SatisFactory - A collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing satisfaction and working experience in smart factory environments*

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT AND PURPOSE OF USE (BACKGROUND)

SatisFactory aims to enhance and enrich the manufacturing working environment towards attractive factories of the future that encompass key enabling technologies such as augmented reality, wearable and ubiquitous computing as well as and customised social communication platforms coupled with experience design and gamification techniques for the efficient transfer of knowledge and experience among employees.

The ultimate goal is to develop and deploy emerging knowledge-driven training techniques (gamification aware) and wearable devices (AR-enabled Glasses) for the enhancement of innovation, productivity and scheduling of work in the production line while enriching its flexibility through the support of team interactions in the shop floor which consequently will add to the work-related satisfaction. Special attention in the deployment of cutting-edge incentives (wearable computing, gamified working experience) will be given towards further increase of attractiveness to the younger generation.

Project Objectives and Expected Results

The project foresees to achieve its main goals through multi-disciplinary technologies stemming from the deployment of a “plug-and-share” multi-sensorial framework for collecting effectively tacit knowledge generated in the factory environment, the delivery of a semantically enriched knowledge modelling framework (based on envisioned Common Information Data Exchange Model - CIDEM) for supporting on job education of workers as well as for incident management and proactive maintenance, whereas it will provide the capability to automatically verify the correctness of actions performed by the operators in the field, which accommodated by novel head-mounted displays (next generation AR Glasses provided by GlassUp partner). In parallel, the focus on user experience and gamification will ensure optimal balance between workers performance and satisfaction.

The specific technical project objectives and the corresponding expected results are summarised as follows:

Objective 1: Context-aware control and re-adaptation of shop floor production facilities for increased productivity and flexibility in use of shop floor resources.

SatisFactory will introduce a novel multi-sensorial framework to collect multi-modal data from the shop floor related to thermal and optical data of production outputs, workplace occupancy data, numeric measurements such as temperature, acceleration, vibration, and distension, which will be aggregated and processed, creating a semantically enhanced base of knowledge.

Objective 2: Improvement of attractiveness and productivity through collaboration, social interaction and gamification approaches.

SatisFactory will integrate novel concepts to the factory processes enhancing productivity through increased engagement of workers in the processes and through the stimulation of collaboration. To this end, user experience and gamification approaches will be developed, along with the introduction of a social collaboration platform, in which workers may exchange work knowledge / experiences / practices.

Objective 3: Real-time knowledge-sharing and AR-based collaboration and training services.

SatisFactory will create a knowledge base for the training of employees, along with the development of augmented reality (AR) technologies for delivering interactive training services, within an attractive ambient environment.

Objective 4: Improved shop floor feedback and decision making for gains in productivity, workers wellbeing and comfort.

SatisFactory will implement a decision-making system, which will be able to combine corroborating sources of evidence in terms of real-time data coming from the shop floor and aggregate dynamic information from production activities and critical human-centric and machinery related operations. It could offer feedback to the shop floor in terms of actionable knowledge and recommendations, including maintenance operations and schedules, utilizing AR and visual analytics technologies.

Objective 5: Adaptive and augmented interfaces for collaboration, knowledge sharing and real time support.

SatisFactory will enable real-time communication of information and knowledge among factory actors, either at their workplaces or on the move, using situated embodied interaction technologies enabled by wearable, adaptive and context-aware embedded devices and AR enabled glasses.

Objective 6: Deployment and Evaluation of the solution to large-scale Industrial Facilities from the Automotive and Energy factory domains.

SatisFactory will deploy and evaluate software and hardware products and the entire system to a pre-trial industrial lab (CERTH), and to two large-scale industrial facilities (COMAU with 23 different operative centres, 15 manufacturing plants, and 3 research and development centres in 6 EU Member States and throughout the world, and SUNLIGHT with 2 plants and 12 production/assembly lines).

SatisFactory SELECTED PILOT SITES

In order to test the deployment of the final system and measure the direct effects of SatisFactory developments in real world applications, two real-life industrial environments are selected (COMAU, SUNLIGHT) in the framework of SatisFactory, and one Industrial Lab Use Case (CERTH).

Application Scenarios/Use Cases and Pilot Trials for Evaluation of the envisaged solutions

SatisFactory will be validated in a series of scenarios and use cases designed to cover the most important aspects of the system and be possible to realize within the running period of the project. The following use cases show the possibilities of the proposed framework and they will form the basis for the development of SatisFactory.

1. Increase attractiveness of the Industrial Environment

One main disadvantage of industrial environments that discourages people from seeking a career in this field is the usual unattractiveness of the workplace in factories. Industrial workers usually have to deal with simple displays with minimum informational content and use difficult to handle and dangerous machinery. In addition, some types of work are mainly focused on the repetition of a task that can be both physically and mentally exhausting. Customisable augmented reality tools and functionalities will give to the employees the ability to control some aspects of his view of the working environment.

2. Communication platform for increased interaction between employees

One fundamental drawback of most industrial environments is that they do not allow easy communication and interaction of employees, especially on work related issues. An employee knows that he/she will have to stop his work and maybe step away from his/her workstation in order to ask for advice from a co-worker who will also have to be interrupted and maybe walk back to the first work station to check the problem of situation. In order to address this issue SatisFactory will realise a communication platform which will be augmented with attractive presentation and monitoring equipment allowing in this way employees to ask for advice instantly presenting their problem through a small camera attached on their HMDs and get feedback directly from someone with more experience, or maybe discuss an idea for a specific problem and work together for an innovative solution that could be adopted by the factory.

3. Continuous training and education of employees for the adaptation of the factory to new market requirements

In order to cope with the constantly and continuously changing market that drives industry, production lines nowadays have to be highly flexible supported by mechanisms for fast training of employees. Satisfactory will address this issue based on the dynamically expanding and semantically enhanced knowledge database. Algorithmic tools for object and task recognition supported by augmented reality will form the basis for employee training on-the-job without the need of the continuous attention of an educator. Easy and direct instruction will appear on the HMDs of trainees describing the next step to be performed. The direct communication will be also available when needed through the previous described communication platform.

4. Support of employees on the field with personalised dynamic information

One of the most useful SatisFactory components in terms of increased productivity but also safety and ergonomics will be a system supporting employees on-the-job without interruptions of difficult

methodologies. One example can be the real time information of the user about work related issues or dangers in his environment e.g. time for a component to arrive in the workstation or indication on a pipe of high temperature. In order to increase productivity and efficiently control the scheduling of the tasks of employees, instructions can be directly communicated to the employees informing them about what should be their next focus and how to manage timing related issues.

5. Real-Time Response of the manufacturing facilities to previously unavailable context-aware information

SatisFactory is promising to provide additional sources of information to this mechanism extending its possible applications. An indicative example could be the complete-shut down of a workstation when an unusual or dangerous incident occurs such as the fall of its operator.

PARTICIPANT SELECTION

All involved personnel working in the aforementioned selected pilot sites have already been notified on the project's objectives and the objective of the interviews and the extraction procedures that will take place during the pilots and have given their preliminary consent in participating in the pilot procedures. All people will be contacted again before the actual pilot preparation phase and will be asked to sign an appropriate consent form, verifying their participation.

DURATION

The total duration of the project's interviews will be one month in total, starting in March 2015. Within this period, the initial preparations for the interview will take place towards analysing the material gathered during the interviews. Due to limited time availability the interviews will be performed when the involved personnel will be available. Therefore, the actual duration of the interview may vary in each selected pilot site (COMAU, SUNLIGHT, CERTH).

ETHICS AND DEONTOLOGY

Regarding the acquisition and storage of human related information, the SatisFactory project has followed the appropriate ethics guidelines. These guidelines aim at preserving the privacy of the user, protecting his/her private data and limiting the risk of interception to the minimum. The integrity of the information is important for the project, and thus the following requirements have been fulfilled:

1. The researcher of the interview will inform the participants with clarity about the procedure of the interviews and the objectives of the data storage and analysis that will results from the analysis of the interview.
2. No sensitive personal data are collected. In no case more personal data will be collected than the necessary ones.
3. A data minimization policy will be adopted at all levels of the project and will be supervised by the ethical/privacy component of the project. This will ensure that no data which are not strictly necessary to the completion of the current study will be collected.
4. No data will be collected without the explicit consent of the individuals.

5. Participants will have the right to access their personal data as well as to their extracted profiling parameters.
6. The user will participate to the study, only after he/she has read, accepted and signed the consent form.
7. Participants will be able to quit the interview at any point, if they wish, without any consequences. He/she can exercise his/her right to access and delete his/her data at any moment.

Consent to Participate in Research Interviews

Procedures

If you agree to participate in this research study, an interview will be conducted with you at a time and location of your availability. The interview will involve questions about the daily operations and your collaboration with the other co-workers. It should last about two (2) hours. With your permission, I will audiotape and take notes during the interview. The recording is to accurately record the information you provide, and will be used for transcription purposes only. If you choose not to be audiotaped, I will take notes instead. If you agree to being audiotaped but feel uncomfortable at any time during the interview, the recorder can be turned off at your request. Or if you don't wish to continue, you can stop the interview at any time.

One interview is expected to be conducted. However, follow-ups may be needed for added clarification. If so, I will contact you by mail/phone to request this.

Confidentiality

Your data will be handled as confidentially as possible and will be pseudo-anonymized. If results of this study are published or presented, individual names and other personally identifiable information will not be used. When the research is completed, the audio related material will be deleted. The same measures described above will be taken to protect confidentiality of this study data.

Rights

Participation in research is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to take part in the project. You can decline to answer any questions and are free to stop taking part in the project at any time. Whether or not you choose to participate in the research and whether or not you choose to answer a question or continue participating in the project, there will be no penalty to you or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled.

Questions

If you have any questions about this research, please feel free to contact me. I can be reached at [phone number] or [email address].

CONSENT

I have read the institutes policies regarding the use of human participants and agree to abide by them. I am also familiar with the ethical principles with regard to human participants and the data protection Act. I further agree to submit any significant changes in procedures for additional review.

A copy of this consent will be available upon request.

If you wish to participate in this study, please sign and date below.

Participant:

Name of Participant Signature Date

Researcher:

Name of Researcher Signature Date